

EuroMix

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Validation of the EuroMix model toolbox and comparison with US software

WP 7 – Validation and extrapolation to humans

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1 Introduction

The EuroMix toolbox is a web-based platform including data and models accessible to all key-actors in risk assessment and risk management. The platform includes or links to relevant models to provide estimates of hazard, exposure and risk. The software platform builds on the Monte Carlo Risk Assessment (MCRA) system and is implemented as MCRA version 9.0 (van der Voet et al. 2019). MCRA 9.0 will be available at <https://mcra.rivm.nl> and is currently temporarily available at <https://mcra-test.rivm.nl/EuroMix/WebApp>.

MCRA 9.0 is a modular system contains many models for exposure, hazard and risk assessment (see overview of the 42 modules in van der Voet et al. 2019). Validation of the toolbox as a whole can be broken down into the validation of different parts.

In this report two types of validation are described, internal and external. Internal validation is concerned with checking the software for programming errors and comparing the functionality and outputs of the models against previously released versions. For internal validation all modules of the toolbox are included.

External validation compares the functionality and output of the models against external values generated by another existing software platform. Given the wide functionality of the EuroMix toolbox this is a non-trivial task for the toolbox as a whole. In this document external validation is restricted to the aggregation of dietary and nondietary exposures in the Exposures module. This is compared with similar calculations in the US software SHEDS-HT (Isaacs et al. 2014).

2 Development strategy of the EuroMix toolbox

The software components of the EuroMix toolbox are developed using the concept of ‘continuous integration’. The practices that are used are the following.

2.1 Single source repository

The source code for the EuroMix toolbox is maintained in a Git repository hosted on the Git server of Wageningen University & Research (<https://git.wur.nl>)

All code that is developed is committed to this repository and shared by the developers in the team. The repository contains several branches on which development of features takes place. There is a special mainline branch which contains the source code that contains the latest release of the software, which has been tested and for which a publication package is available for installation on the server(s). The publication packages for all released versions of the EuroMix toolbox are backed up when they are created.

2.2 Automated build

The software components of the EuroMix toolbox are automatically built every night, using the CruiseControl.NET software on a dedicated build server. The build server retrieves the latest development version of the software from the Git repository and builds the components. The release version of the software on the mainline is only built on demand, when a new release is being prepared. A successful build of the software is always followed by the automated tests.

2.3 Automated unit tests

The EuroMix toolbox source code contains unit tests that are configured to run by the CruiseControl software and are designed to safeguard the software when it is being developed and refactored over time. The unit tests are run nightly after a successful build, and are monitored daily by the development team. Any irregularities are usually fixed within a day.

When a software release is planned, the unit tests are run again and a publication package is only created when all tests have passed successfully.

2.4 Automated regression testing

After a successful build and unit testing cycle, the latest version of the software is tested against the currently released (previous) version of the software by running a set of predefined MCRA projects that cover the application’s broad range of different settings and data inputs. The output that is generated is automatically compared and differences are readily reported to the development team.

2.5 Automated deployment to test server

The EuroMix toolbox software is deployed to the test server environment accessible at <https://mcra.test.wur.nl/euromix/webapp> every night after a successful build and test cycle.

This automatic deployment updates the database server, the job scheduler, simulation worker and web server software to the current development build version.

2.6 Visibility of current state of development

The CruiseControl.NET server hosts a website which always shows the latest state of the system and any build, test or deployment cycles that are in progress. The development team members get notified whenever a build, test or deployment fails and can take action accordingly.

3 Internal components of the EuroMix toolbox

To better understand the scope and results of the various unit tests reported in the next chapter, an overview of the components that make up the EuroMix toolbox is given here.

Generally four types of components can be discerned, core components, data access components, utility components and user interface components. A short explanation of these categories is given below.

3.1 Core components

These are the components that contain the so-called business logic of the application, which in the case of the EuroMix toolbox are the calculators and simulation models which process and transform the input data into valuable output. Evidently, these components are the main focus of the validation tests described in this document.

3.2 Data access components

These components are responsible for retrieving the data for processing by the core components from the database and/or input files that are uploaded. Data management including user/groups authorization and storage are also handled by these components.

3.3 Utility components

Utility components are used throughout the application and provide general functionality that is used in most other components. These also include third party components that contain necessary functionality for the core components, for example a library to be able to include R to process certain calculations.

3.4 User interface components

The user interface components make up the part of the EuroMix toolbox that is visible to the user. The application's front end consists of a user interface which runs in the user's web browser and the user interface controller which runs on the web server.

4 Internal validation of the EuroMix toolbox

4.1 Unit testing

As mentioned in paragraph 2.3, unit testing is a validation step in the software development process, which provides validation of software code at the lowest level by testing individual software functions. In test driven development, for every software function one or more unit tests are written that check the inputs and outputs of each function and make sure they are correct and consistent over time. Ideally, the unit tests for a function are written before the code of the function itself.

The EuroMix toolbox is developed using continuous integration, where the code is built and unit tests are run on a daily basis. All unit tests must pass before a new version of the software is released.

4.2 Code coverage

Code coverage measures the part of the component's source code which is covered by unit tests. In the past development of MCRA, the focus was mostly laid on integration testing, in which the software as a whole is validated using data sets coming from real-world scenarios and unit tests were usually written with the purpose of testing elaborate software procedures as a whole. Now that the software has grown as new functionalities are being added and elaborate procedures are broken

down into multiple interacting and reused parts, the strategy is changing towards more concise and reusable software procedures which contain less code but have more interaction, unit testing these components becomes more appropriate.

The code coverage results show two types of coverage, line coverage and branch coverage. Line coverage counts the occurrences of statements that are called by the unit tests, whereas branch coverage also counts whether all paths through a statement are covered, which depends on the amount of 'if' statements there are in the tested statement.

In the following paragraphs, the code coverage with unit tests is described for the main software components which make the EuroMix toolbox, as highlighted in chapter 3.

4.2.1 Component 'Biometris'

This utility component contains a library of functions and procedures which are used throughout the other components in the EuroMix toolbox. These include statistics functions, a connector for running R code, file readers for reading and writing of XML, CSV, Excel, and other types of files, creating visuals for graphs and charts, random generators and many more.

Code coverage results

	MCRA 8	MCRA 9
Assemblies	1	1
Classes	108	117
Files	104	113
Covered lines	1282	1504
Uncovered lines	5451	5713
Coverable lines	6733	7217
Total lines	18197	20028
Line coverage	19% (1282 of 6733)	20.8% (1504 of 7217)
Covered branches	489	554
Total branches	3202	3545
Branch coverage	15.2% (489 of 3202)	15.6% (554 of 3545)

4.2.2 Component 'MCRA.Data.Management'

This component contains the core data access components that are used in the simulation, job scheduler and user interface components.

Code coverage results

	MCRA 8	MCRA 9
Assemblies	1	1
Classes	61	47
Files	59	77
Covered lines	562	3634
Uncovered lines	4093	2786
Coverable lines	4655	6420
Total lines	9101	12391
Line coverage	12% (562 of 4655)	56.6% (3634 of 6420)

Covered branches	172	1247
Total branches	1782	2598
Branch coverage	9.6% (172 of 1782)	47.9% (1247 of 2598)

4.2.3 Component 'MCRA.General'

This utility component contains general MCRA functionality which is used throughout the EuroMix toolbox. The functionality in this component is specific to MCRA, so it is not placed in the 'Biometris' component. It consists of MCRA data formats, specifications and definitions. These definitions are specified and administered in XML files, from which code is generated. Unit testing for this component was only introduced during development of the EuroMix toolbox, so for MCRA 8 no results are displayed.

Code coverage results

	MCRA 8	MCRA 9
Assemblies	No tests	1
Classes	-	85
Files	-	79
Covered lines	-	713
Uncovered lines	-	1059
Coverable lines	-	1772
Total lines	-	5229
Line coverage	-	40.2% (713 of 1772)
Covered branches	-	365
Total branches	-	1178
Branch coverage	-	30.9% (365 of 1178)

4.2.4 Component 'MCRA.ProjectEntityModels'

This component contains all data access related functionality for user project settings and metadata. This project administration is conceptually different from the data management component previously described, which is about the data that is used inside of a project.

Code coverage results

	MCRA 8	MCRA 9
Assemblies	1	1
Classes	122	110
Files	139	143
Covered lines	1124	1397
Uncovered lines	724	565
Coverable lines	1848	1962
Total lines	5796	5818
Line coverage	60.8% (1124 of 1848)	71.2% (1397 of 1962)
Covered branches	64	63
Total branches	447	323

Branch coverage	14.3% (64 of 447)	19.5% (63 of 323)
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4.2.5 Component 'MCRA.Simulation'

This component contains the implementation of the modular design of the EuroMix toolbox. It is the main component of the application's core functionality.

Code coverage results

	MCRA 8	MCRA 9
Assemblies	1	1
Classes	626	926
Files	615	895
Covered lines	2667	10895
Uncovered lines	25793	24780
Coverable lines	28460	35675
Total lines	55820	71463
Line coverage	9.3% (2667 of 28460)	30.5% (10895 of 35675)
Covered branches	570	3589
Total branches	12585	15128
Branch coverage	4.5% (570 of 12585)	23.7% (3589 of 15128)

4.3 Integration testing

Integration testing is a validation step which tests the interaction between the cooperating software components to make sure the software as a whole functions correctly. Integration tests are usually implemented using a unit test framework. In this case use case scenarios are tested spanning multiple components instead of individual functions in a single component. All integration tests must pass before a new version of the software is released.

4.4 Integration test results

The integration tests are implemented as unit tests which span multiple components and are as such not suitable for code coverage reporting. Instead, a global indicator of the amount of tests that have been run is as follows:

Results for MCRA 8:

Number of Tests	Passed
69	69

Results for MCRA 9:

Number of Tests	Passed
70	70

See appendix A.1 for detailed test results containing a description of the unit tested scenarios in MCRA 8 and appendix A.2 for those of the EuroMix toolbox (MCRA 9).

4.5 Regression testing

Regression testing validates that new versions of the software don't introduce so-called 'regressions', which are accidental faults introduced into previously validated parts of the software. Regression testing is performed daily and consists of running a predefined set of projects and comparing the results to the results of an earlier version. In this report, MCRA 9 (the EuroMix toolbox) is validated against MCRA 8.

The results from the regression tests are automatically compared using the continuous integration pipeline. Comparison is done at two levels, first and foremost, the percentile output tables of the exposure assessments are compared. This is the key indicator of a possible breaking change in the software, which would need further investigation. The second level of comparison involves all other output tables that are generated during a simulation run, which are also automatically compared.

The following paragraphs contain the outcomes for the validation tests that are run during the nightly build and validation process.

An overview of the regression tests scenarios that were run can be found in the following table. In the comparison column, the comparison result of the percentiles tables in the detailed results in the appendix is summarized here.

Nr	Test name	Comparison MCRA 8 and EuroMix toolbox (MCRA 9)
1	Acute cumulative exposure assessment with generated data	Identical
2	Acute custom cumulative exposure assessment	Identical
3	Acute cumulative exposure assessment	Identical
4	Chronic cumulative exposure assessment	Differences in percentiles in 'model based' percentiles are the result of code changes which have altered the propagation of random seeding. Running the project with different seeds gives the same variance in resulting percentiles.
5	Chronic cumulative exposure assessment	Differences in 'model based' percentiles, because of changes in random seeding.
6	Chronic TDS (total diet study) exposure assessment	Differences in 'model based' percentiles, because of changes in random seeding.
7	Acute cumulative aggregate exposure assessment	Identical
8	Acute cumulative exposure assessment, pessimistic	Identical
9	Acute cumulative exposure assessment, pessimistic	Differences in 'model based' percentiles, because of changes in random seeding.
10	Acute cumulative exposure assessment, optimistic	Identical
11	Acute cumulative exposure assessment	Identical

	with focal commodity	
12	Acute cumulative exposure assessment	Identical
13	Acute cumulative health impact, hazard (ipra) assessment	Identical
14	Acute pessimistic cumulative exposure assessment	Identical
15	Acute, short term exposure assessment	Identical
16	Acute exposure assessment, optimistic	Identical
17	Acute exposure assessment, pessimistic	Identical
18	Chronic cumulative exposure assessment, optimistic	Identical
19	Chronic cumulative exposure assessment 'apple' subset	Identical
20	Chronic cumulative exposure assessment 'dates' subset	Identical
21	Chronic cumulative exposure assessment, pessimistic	Identical
22	Chronic cumulative exposure assessment, pessimistic, F20-25	Identical
23	Health impact	Identical
24	Chronic cumulative exposure assessment, pessimistic, M20-25	Identical
25	Chronic exposure assessment	Identical
26	Chronic exposure assessment, Betabinomial normal model	Differences in 'model based' percentiles, because of changes in random seeding.
27	Chronic exposure assessment, model ISUF	Identical
28	Chronic exposure assessment, model LNN with correlation	Differences in 'model based' percentiles, because of changes in random seeding.
29	Chronic exposure assessment, model LNN	Differences in 'model based' percentiles, because of changes in random seeding.
30	Chronic exposure assessment, model OIM	Identical
31	Chronic exposure assessment, model-then-add	Differences in 'model based' percentiles, because of changes in random seeding.
32	TDS Chronic, long term exposure	Identical

	assessment	
33	TDS Chronic, long term exposure assessment, Multigrain B+R	Identical

For a detailed description of the tests including the data and settings that were used, and an explanation of some differences that were found, see appendix A.3.

5 External validation: comparison of aggregate exposure calculation with US software

5.1 Introduction

The objective is to compare the probabilistic approach developed in the EuroMix Toolbox to aggregate exposure with the one proposed by the US-EPA in the SHEDS models. Both software programs are based on a probabilistic approach and use Monte-Carlo simulations to estimate the population exposure to substances present in different sources (diet, air, dust, water, cosmetics, etc.) and which enter in the body by different routes (ingestion, inhalation, and dermal contact). A comparison of dietary exposure assessment between SHEDS-dietary (DEEM) and MCRA was done with success in the Acropolis project (van der Voet et al. 2015). Thus, the key point here is to validate the way that the two software programs aggregate the dietary with the non-dietary exposure. For that, some results of the case study on aggregate and cumulative exposure to pyrethroids done in Deliverable 5.4 on aggregate exposure was used.

5.2 SHEDS models

The SHEDS (Stochastics Stochastic Human Exposure and Dose Simulation) models are probabilistic models that can estimate exposures people face from chemicals encountered in everyday activities (Figure 1). The models are able to generate predictions of aggregate and cumulative exposures over time to inform risk assessments that protect human health. SHEDS models estimate the range of total chemical exposures in a population from four exposure pathways: inhalation, skin contact, and dietary and non-dietary ingestion over different time periods. These estimates are calculated using available data such as dietary consumption surveys; human activity from the Consolidated Human Activity Database (CHAD); and observed or modeled levels in food, water, air and on surfaces like counters and floors. The data on chemical concentrations and exposure factors used in SHEDS are based in measurements collected in EPA field studies and published literature. SHEDS can also help identify critical exposure pathways, factors and uncertainties.

Figure 1. Sheds general approach

EPA has developed a number of different SHEDS models and modules that address specific research questions about chemical exposure.

SHEDS-Multimedia, v3 is currently available via free download. It is a physically-based, probabilistic model that can simulate cumulative (multiple chemicals) or aggregate (single chemical) exposures over time for a population via residential and dietary routes of exposure. SHEDS-Multimedia uses both the SHEDS-Residential and SHEDS-Dietary models to predict ranges of exposure in a population; identify critical pathways, factors and uncertainties; and enhance dose model estimates.

SHEDS-Dietary v.1 is a probabilistic, population-based dietary exposure assessment module of SHEDS-Multimedia. It can simulate individual exposures to chemicals in food and drinking water over different time periods (e.g., daily, yearly).

SHEDS-Residential v. 4 is a probabilistic, population-based residential exposure assessment module of SHEDS-Multimedia. It can simulate cumulative (multiple chemicals) or aggregate (single chemical) residential exposures over time via multiple routes of exposure for different types of chemicals and scenarios. These models are linked together with structure-based physiologically-based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) models and are used together to quantify target tissue dose, and conduct linked exposure-dose model evaluations.

SHEDS-High throughput (SHEDS-HT) — currently in beta form — can produce exposure estimates for thousands of chemicals in a rapid and cost-effective manner. It offers more flexibility for inputs than SHEDS-Multimedia, and can quickly provide exposure estimates for new chemicals that have limited data, and can provide information to help prioritize chemicals for future study on the basis of risk (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Sheds HT sources and routes of exposure

5.3 Aggregate exposure in the EuroMix toolbox

The EuroMix toolbox combines dietary exposure estimated by MCRA with non-dietary exposure estimated by external software programs described in Figure 3. Non-dietary individual exposures can be explicitly matched to individual dietary records by linking individual identifiers (1) or can be randomly assigned (2). The first case corresponds to the rare case where the information on diet and non-diet exposure is available for the same individuals. In that case, correlations between an individual’s dietary and non-dietary exposure are automatically taken into account. When the dietary and non-dietary exposures are estimated from two different populations (second case), correlations can be included in an indirect way, by randomly assigning non-dietary exposure records to the diets of sampled individuals but conditional on matching age and/or sex. The matching of dietary and non-dietary records takes place as part of the general Monte Carlo simulation. By performing multiple uncertainty loops, the entire process can be repeated so that uncertainty due to the matching can be included in the output. More details are given in the functional design of the Milestone MS10 of WP6 and Deliverables 6.1 and 6.2 on the EuroMix toolbox. Also Euromix case studies of the Deliverables 5.4 use the EuroMix toolbox to aggregate exposures to pesticides and Bisphenols (Kennedy et al. 2019, Vanacker et al. Submitted, Karrer Submitted).

Figure 3. Scheme of the links between dietary and non-dietary softwares in the EuroMix toolbox

5.4 The case study of pyrethroids

In the Deliverable 5.4, ANSES was in charge of a cumulative and aggregate case study on pyrethroids. The different sources and routes of exposure to cyfluthrin, cypermethrin, deltamethrin and permethrin were taken into account to estimate the exposure of the adult population in France (See Figure 4 for more details). Dietary exposure estimated with MCRA was coupled in the EuroMix toolbox with a probabilistic exposure model for non-dietary exposure implemented in an R-Shiny application (RSExp).

Figure 4. Concept map of the assessment of aggregate and cumulative exposures to pyrethroids in French adult population

5.5 Methodology to compare SHEDS and the EuroMix toolbox for aggregate exposure

As a case study to compare the two software programs, exposures to deltamethrin and permethrin by ingestion through diet and dust were chosen from the results of Deliverable 5.4, which focused on aggregate exposure. These two substances were the ones contributing the most to the cumulative exposure and to the metabolite urine concentrations of the 4 pyrethroids. After studying the different SHEDS models (SHEDS-multimedia, SHEDS-residential, SHEDS-dietary and SHEDS-High throughput) and consulting Kristin Isaac (Isaacs et al. 2014), from the US-EPA, it was decided to compare the EuroMix toolbox to SHEDS-High throughput. R software was also used to generate values for some input variables.

5.5.1 Aggregate exposure generated under SHEDS-HT

SHEDS-HT is available in an R package and many files are available to compute the program for the American population. Thus, to run the program, the user needs to create an input data set including 11 files (Table 1).

Table 1. Input data and files for SHEDS-HT software (Isaacs and Glen 2017)

File	Description	Source for default information
Run file	List of job settings for this model run	User-defined
Activity diary file	Daily location (time spent in microenvironments) and activity (physical activity index PAI, a time-averaged metabolic equivalent) information for each age- and gender-specific CHAD diary	Calculated from USEPA's CHAD (McCurdy et al. 2000, U.S. EPA 2014)
Chemical property file	Chemical-specific property information by CAS numbers	Chemical Properties from ORD's CompTox Dashboard where available; either OPERA model predictions or means or reported measured values; other values derived from EPI Suite (U.S. EPA 2012)
Dietary diary file	Daily mass of food group consumed by individuals	Calculated from NHANES-WWEIA food diaries (USDA 2014)
Exposure factor File	Distributions for various human exposure factors	Literature
Fugacity file	Distributions for house variables needed for fugacity modeling	Literature
Media file	List of media in each micro that may contain chemicals	N/A
Physiology file	Body mass, height, and basal metabolic rate distributions or regressions by age/gender cohort	Developed for SHEDS-Multimedia from NHANES (Glen et al. 2012)
Population file	Number of individuals in US in each age/gender cohort	2000 US Census (US Census Bureau 2000)
Source scenario file	Lists of active exposure scenarios for each potential source	User-Defined
Source chemical file	Distributions of variables dependent on both source and chemical	User-Defined
Source variable file	Distributions of source-specific variables	User-Defined

Dietary exposure was generated from SHEDS HT, in combining American data on diet consumption, concentration of deltamethrin and permethrin in food and physiological characteristics of individuals available from the software. The food residue scenario covers ingestion exposure that is, eating and drinking, to chemicals left on the food as residue. SHEDS divides foods (including drinks) into multiple user-defined categories. There are two input files that are used by this scenario, and the same food category definitions must be used on each. The diet diary file reports daily food consumption by food category for a large number of individuals, each labelled by age and gender cohort. For all categories, the units are grams per day. The second input file is the source chemicals file, which, among other things, reports the distribution of chemical concentration in each food category, for each chemical (Isaacs and Glen 2017). Then, the dietary exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{day}$) of each category was assessed by the following equation:

$$exp. diet = consumption \times residue \quad (1)$$

Where consumption is the amount of this food type consumed (g/day) available in the diet dairy file, and residue, the chemical residue in food ($\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$) in the source chemicals file. Permethrin and deltamethrin were observed in different sources of food (Table 2).

In the deliverable 5.4, dust exposure by ingestion $EO_{\text{dust};ij}$ was calculated from the equation:

$$EO_{\text{dust};ij} = \frac{C_{\text{dust};i} \times Q_{\text{dust};j} \times 10^{-3}}{BW_j} \quad (2)$$

The quantity of ingested dust for each individual $Q_{\text{dust},j}$ (mg/kg) were simulated for the American population from R software with lognormal distributions with parameters from Özkaynak et al. (2011) and truncated between 0 and 1000 following the recommendations from the Exposure Factors Handbook (U.S. EPA 2011). Observed dust concentrations from the deliverable D5.4 on aggregate exposure were very low and thus aggregate exposure was similar to dietary exposure. To be able to distinguish dust exposure from dietary exposure, dust concentrations of permethrin and deltamethrin were boosted in multiplying observed concentration by 1000. The distribution of the concentration in dust $C_{\text{dust},i}$ of permethrin and deltamethrin was added in the source chemicals file as proposed in the Deliverable 5.4 from observed data (Table 2).

In SHEDS-HT for the lognormal distribution, the arithmetic mean and the CV are transformed automatically into the geometric mean (GM) and the geometric standard deviation (GSD) by the equations 3 and 4. Then, the lognormal distributions are imputed by the relationships between GM/GSD with the mean (μ) and the standard deviation (δ) of the logarithmic distribution (equation 5 and 6).

$$GM = \frac{\text{mean}}{\sqrt{1+CV^2}} \quad (3)$$

$$GSD = e^{\sqrt{\log(1+CV^2)}} \quad (4)$$

$$\mu = \ln(GM) \quad (5)$$

$$\delta = \ln(GSD) \quad (6)$$

Dietary exposure and dust exposures of the American population were then automatically aggregated under the SHEDS HT.

Table 2. Distribution parameters of concentrations ($\mu\text{g/g}$) of permethrin and deltamethrin in foods and in dust implemented in SHEDS-HT package. Mean is the arithmetic mean of the distribution and CV the coefficient of variation (equal to the standard deviation divided by the arithmetic mean).

Source of exposure	Description	Permethrin				Deltamethrin				
		Mean	CV	Distribution	Detects/Nondetects	Mean	CV	Distribution	Detects/Nondetects	
Dietary exposure	BF	Beef	0.017	0.392	lognormal	5/0				
	BR	Brassica leafy vegetables	1.77	1.13	lognormal	102/0	0.02	0	lognormal	49/0
	CF	Citrus fruits	0.127	0	point	1/0				
	CG	Cereals grains	0.041	1.13	lognormal	43/0	0.02	0	point	4/0
	CV	Curcubit vegetables	0.081	0.637	lognormal	19/0	0.025	0	point	2/0
	DP	Dairy products	0.007	1.39	lognormal	83/0				
	EG	Egg	0.027	0.419	lognormal	2/0				
	FI	Fish					0.012	0	point	1/0
	FV	Fruiting vegetables	0.084	0.594	lognormal	111/0	0.05	0.659	lognormal	14/0
	HO	Honey	0.011	0	point	1/0				
	LE	Leafy vegetables	1.96	1.12	lognormal	2455/0	0.025	0	point	1/0
	LV	Legume vegetables	0.028	1.8	lognormal	19/0	0.052	1.09	lognormal	11/0
	PF	Pome fruits	0.056	0.135	lognormal	2/0				
	RT	Root or tuber vegetables	0.021	0	point	3/0				
Non-dietary exposure	Dust	Dust in homes	22.13	6.33	lognormal	145/0	0.248	8.69	lognormal	145/0

5.5.2 Aggregate exposure generated with the EuroMix toolbox

Dietary exposure was performed using the EuroMix toolbox in combining the previous American data on dietary consumption, physiological characteristics of individuals available in SHEDS-HT with concentrations generated in R software with similar parameters entered in SHEDS-HT in 5.1 as the EuroMix toolbox does not have the option to generate values from distributions.

Dust exposure in $\mu\text{g}/\text{day}$ was entirely calculated under R software in using the same values generated in 5.1 for the ingested quantity and in simulated values for concentration using the same parameterized distributions.

Dietary exposure and dust exposure of the American population was then aggregated under the EuroMix toolbox (Table 3).

In this study, only the aggregate exposure was evaluate for each substance, thus no toxicological effect file was considered, and no cumulative exposure was applied. Furthermore, no processing factors and no processing type was recorded in SHEDS-HT files. Thus, in the ProcessingFactors file, value of 1 was recorded in nominal and upper column of each category of foods. In the ProcessingType, the value of 2 which represent a lognormal distribution was recorded for the distribution type, and a value of 0 was recorded for the column BulkingBlending.

Table 3. Input data and files for MCRA 9.0 software modified from files in SHEDS-HT.

File	Description
FoodConsumption	Consumption of each individual for each category food. The food survey include 2 days of survey for almost all individuals.
Individuals	Body weight, age, gender, and identification of each individual.
FoodSurvey	Description of the survey, include the number of observed days, and the unit of body weight and age.
ConcentrationsSSD	Residue concentrations recorded for each food category for the both substances
NonDietarySurveys	Description of the non-dietary surveys
NonDietaryAbsorptionFactors	Oral absorption factor for each substance in the different surveys
NonDietarySurveyProperties	Characteristics of the population in the different non-dietary surveys
NonDietaryExposures	Individual values of non-dietary exposures for each substance
Food	Description of food categories
Substances	Description of substances
Effect	Description of effect, not used
ProcessingFactors	Processing factors for each substance and in each food category, set to 1
ProcessingType	Processing type of each food category, set to 2 and 0

5.6 Result comparisons

Comparison of result types

Comparisons of result types between the two softwares are summarized in table 4. SHEDS-HT provides statistics on the total population and on different subpopulations like men, women, pregnant women, children, etc (Table 4). It also took into account the kinetic properties of the

chemical, and proposed exposure after the potential abortion of the substance in the gastro intestinal tract. The EuroMix toolbox provides uncertainty intervals and shows more outputs than SHEDS-HT, like for example the figure of distributions.

Table 4. Comparison of result types between SEHDS-HT and EuroMix toolbox

	SHEDS-HT	Euromix toolbox
Statistics of aggregate exposure by routes	Exposures are assessed by routes	Exposures are assessed by routes with a distinction between dietary and non-dietary ingestions
Statistics of high percentiles	None	Statistics for the most exposed individuals
Uncertainty	Does not show uncertainty	Uncertainty intervals
Figures and Tables	Only outputs with tables (.csv)	Figures of distributions / pie chart of exposure contributions and tables
Subpopulation	Proposes directly the exposure of different cohorts (women, men, pregnant women, children, etc.)	Needs to run each cohort separately to have specific exposure
Internal exposures	Takes into account the chemical properties of each substance to assess exposure via the gastrointestinal absorption	A PBPK model may be added to evaluate internal exposure

Aggregate exposure results to deltamethrin and permethrin

Aggregate exposures of deltamethrin and permethrin were assessed with SHEDS-HT and the EuroMix toolbox (Table 5 and 6). Globally the results between the two softwares were similar. Indeed, results from SHEDS for external aggregate exposures were within the range of the uncertainty intervals obtained with the EuroMix toolbox. However, significant differences were observed for the most exposed individuals from the 80th percentiles for the two substances (figures 5 and 6). For deltamethrin and permethrin, high levels of percentiles were lower with SHEDS-HT than those observed with EuroMix toolbox.

Table 5. Aggregate exposure to deltamethrin (µg/kg/day) with SHEDS-HT and EuroMix toolbox

	Results from SHEDS-HT	Results from EuroMix Toolbox		
Statistics	Aggregate exposure µg/kg/day	Aggregate exposure µg/kg/day	Non-dietary exposure µg/kg/day	Dietary exposure µg/kg/day

1%	0.03	0.0308 [0.0281 - 0.0351]	0.0001 [0.00008 - 0.0001]	0.0200 [0.0175 - 0.0219]
2.50%	0.04	0.0434 [0.0396 - 0.0491]	0.0002 [0.0002 - 0.0002]	0.0304 [0.0269 - 0.0337]
5%	0.06	0.0572 [0.0519 - 0.065]	0.0004 [0.0004 - 0.0005]	0.041 [0.0369 - 0.0459]
10%	0.08	0.0757 [0.0683 - 0.0866]	0.0010 [0.0010 - 0.0011]	0.0567 [0.0508 - 0.0629]
15%	0.09	0.0912 [0.082 - 0.105]	0.0018 [0.0017 - 0.0019]	0.0687 [0.0608 - 0.076]
20%	0.11	0.105 [0.0950 - 0.121]	0.0028 [0.0028 - 0.0029]	0.0797 [0.0702 - 0.0888]
25%	0.12	0.119 [0.107 - 0.139]	0.0042 [0.0040 - 0.0043]	0.0899 [0.0791 - 0.101]
30%	0.13	0.133 [0.12 - 0.154]	0.0060 [0.0058 - 0.0062]	0.100 [0.088 - 0.112]
40%	0.17	0.161 [0.146 - 0.188]	0.011 [0.011 - 0.012]	0.121 [0.106 - 0.136]
50%	0.20	0.197 [0.179 - 0.229]	0.020 [0.020 - 0.021]	0.144 [0.126 - 0.162]
60%	0.25	0.244 [0.221 - 0.282]	0.037 [0.036 - 0.038]	0.171 [0.149 - 0.193]
70%	0.31	0.311 [0.284 - 0.359]	0.070 [0.067 - 0.072]	0.206 [0.180 - 0.234]
75%	0.36	0.360 [0.328 - 0.416]	0.100 [0.096 - 0.104]	0.229 [0.201 - 0.261]
80%	0.42	0.432 [0.393 - 0.494]	0.151 [0.145 - 0.157]	0.258 [0.225 - 0.294]
85%	0.52	0.541 [0.499 - 0.615]	0.240 [0.231 - 0.249]	0.297 [0.259 - 0.338]
90%	0.70	0.749 [0.693 - 0.836]	0.441 [0.422 - 0.470]	0.354 [0.308 - 0.406]
95%	1.18	1.374 [1.295 - 1.506]	1.07 [1.02 - 1.16]	0.454 [0.393 - 0.526]
97.50%	2.04	2.667 [2.475 - 2.891]	2.36 [2.18 - 2.61]	0.564 [0.484 - 0.655]
99%	4.29	6.272 [5.661 - 7.018]	5.30 [5.40 - 6.67]	0.735 [0.611 - 0.869]
99.50%	7.31	11.32 [10.24 - 12.51]	11.08 [9.82 - 12.19]	0.885 [0.713 - 1.04]
mean	0.46	0.548 [0.5058 - 0.6004]	0.364 [0.319 - 0.412]	0.184 [0.161 - 0.211]

Figure 5. Aggregate exposure to deltamethrin (µg/kg/day) with SHEDS-HT and EuroMix toolbox

Table 6. Aggregate exposure to permethrin ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}/\text{day}$) with SHEDS-HT and EuroMix toolbox

	Results from SHEDS-HT	Results from EuroMix Toolbox		
Statistics	Aggregate exposure $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}/\text{day}$	Aggregate exposure $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}/\text{day}$	Non-dietary exposure $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}/\text{day}$	Dietary exposure $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}/\text{day}$
1%	0.21	0.22 [0.21 - 0.26]	0.016 [0.015 - 0.017]	0.055 [0.046 - 0.066]
2.50%	0.33	0.34 [0.31 - 0.37]	0.034 [0.032 - 0.037]	0.088 [0.076 - 0.105]
5%	0.47	0.49 [0.46 - 0.53]	0.068 [0.065 - 0.071]	0.126 [0.110 - 0.151]
10%	0.73	0.76 [0.71 - 0.80]	0.15 [0.14 - 0.15]	0.188 [0.167 - 0.2182]
15%	0.99	1.02 [0.97 - 1.08]	0.25 [0.24 - 0.27]	0.245 [0.222 - 0.283]
20%	1.26	1.32 [1.26 - 1.38]	0.38 [0.37 - 0.39]	0.306 [0.278 - 0.348]
25%	1.56	1.67 [1.56 - 1.7]	0.55 [0.53 - 0.58]	0.366 [0.336 - 0.414]
30%	1.90	2.00 [1.91 - 2.07]	0.774 [0.7428 - 0.801]	0.434 [0.401 - 0.492]
40%	2.74	2.89 [2.79 - 2.99]	1.404 [1.358 - 1.447]	0.601 [0.554 - 0.661]
50%	3.93	4.12 [3.96 - 4.24]	2.484 [2.396 - 2.57]	0.816 [0.761 - 0.882]
60%	5.76	6.06 [5.85 - 6.24]	4.372 [4.229 - 4.545]	1.091 [1.018 - 1.159]
70%	8.94	9.66 [9.32 - 10.0]	7.895 [7.573 - 8.308]	1.461 [1.368 - 1.561]
75%	11.69	12.74 [12.38 - 13.13]	11.1 [10.75 - 11.65]	1.709 [1.61 - 1.82]
80%	15.75	17.79 [17.24 - 18.73]	16.13 [15.55 - 16.97]	2.017 [1.898 - 2.152]
85%	22.86	26.78 [25.94 - 28.12]	25.22 [24.46 - 26.53]	2.439 [2.287 - 2.608]
90%	37.51	45.96 [43.52 - 48.04]	44.09 [42 - 46.78]	3.051 [2.851 - 3.296]
95%	79.64	102.4 [97.63 - 109]	100.8 [95.6 - 107.8]	4.231 [3.894 - 4.636]
97.50%	157.99	213.7 [197.4 - 228.9]	212 [195.5 - 227]	5.707 [5.173 - 6.321]
99%	343.72	509.6 [452.6 - 578]	506.4 [449.8 - 575.2]	7.867 [7.023 - 8.848]
99.50%	570.70	948.0 [839.8 - 1119]	947.4 [838 - 1117]	9.472 [8.401 - 10.94]
mean	25.02	34.8 [31.45 - 38.81]	33.4 [30.16 - 37.4]	1.35 [1.254 - 1.439]

Figure 6. Aggregate exposure to permethrin ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}/\text{day}$) with SHEDS-HT and EuroMix toolbox

Looking at the contribution of the different sources of exposure between the two softwares (Table 7), some differences can be observed which can explain the differences in high percentiles of aggregated exposure. For example, it was observed that the contribution from dust was higher than from food with EuroMix Toolbox compared to SHEDS-HT. Some food contribution was null with EuroMix Toolbox (citrus, honey...).

Table 7. Contribution to aggregate exposure of permethrin and deltamethrin with the two SHEDS-HT and EuroMix toolbox

Source of exposure	Description	Permethrin		Deltamethrin		
		SHEDS-HT	EuroMix Toolbox	SHEDS-HT	EuroMix Toolbox	
Dietary exposure	BF	Beef	0.1%	0.02%		
	BR	Brassica leafy vegetables	1.9%	1.1%	1.1%	0.6%
	CF	Citrus fruits	0.8%	0		
	CG	Cereals grains	0.8%	0.4%	19%	14%
	CV	Curcubit vegetables	0.1%	0.1%	1.9%	1.2%
	DP	Dairy products	0.2%	0.2%		
	EG	Egg	0.1%	0.04%		
	FI	Fish			0.8%	0.4%
	FV	Fruiting Vegetables	0.4%	0.2%	12.1%	7%
	HO	Honey	0.001%	0		
	LE	Leafy Vegetables	3.5%	1.4%	2.3%	1.2%
	LV	Legume Vegetables	0.1%	0.1%	11.4%	9%
	PF	Pome Fruits	0.3%	0.3%		
	RT	Root or tuber vegetables	0.1%	0.1%		
	Total foods	8%	4%	49%	33%	
Non-dietary exposure	Dust	Dust in homes	92%	96%	51%	67%

5.7 Conclusion

Aggregate exposures of the two pyrethroids were assessed with the SHEDS-HT package in R and with the EuroMix toolbox. Both software programs show similar results except for high percentiles started at the 80th percentile for which SHEDS give lower values than EuroMix Toolbox. Moreover, the EuroMix toolbox takes uncertainty into account and presents more graphical results than SHEDS-HT.

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Appendices

A.1 MCRA 8 integration test results

In the following table, the integration test results are given from the MCRA version 8.

Test report MCRA.Test

This page is automatically generated and summarizes the results of the automated tests for validating the various parts of the system. The main emphasis of the automatic test written for MCRA lies on: testing the data and database integrity, functional testing of individual simulation components, functional testing of complete simulation runs, and load/performance testing of data load operations and complete simulations.

Test date: 2019-04-03T23:39:01.9095562+02:00

ConceptsTests

DynamicMembersTest

Test	Description	Outcome
GetMembers1	<i>No description</i>	Passed

DynamicSectionsTest

Test	Description	Outcome
DynamicSectionsTest1	<i>No description</i>	Passed

EnumAttributesTest

Test	Description	Outcome
GetEnumDisplayAttributeTest	<i>No description</i>	Passed

JobExecuterTests

Test	Description	Outcome
RunExposureScreeningTest	Creates a small test project with default settings and runs a complete simulation.	Passed
RunFoodConversionTest	Creates a small test project with default settings and runs a complete simulation.	Passed
RunIntakeCalculationTest	Creates a small test project with default settings and runs a complete simulation.	Passed
RunSimulationTest	Creates a small test project with default settings and runs a complete simulation.	Passed

ListsCapacityTests

Test	Description	Outcome
ListCapacityTest1	<i>No description</i>	Passed

ParallelPerformanceTests

Test	Description	Outcome
HardcoreParallelTest1	<i>No description</i>	Passed
HardcoreParallelTest2	<i>No description</i>	Passed

Initialization

DirectoryChecks

Test	Description	Outcome
RepositoryPathExistsTest	<i>No description</i>	Passed
TestDataPathExistsTest	<i>No description</i>	Passed

FileChecks

Test	Description	Outcome
CheckIfRepositoryIsAvailable	<i>No description</i>	Passed

IntegrationTests

This section contains integration tests, for validating the interaction between multiple parts of the system.

Data Integrity Tests

This section contains data integrity tests, for validating correct processing of input data.

Agricultural Uses Data Tests

This section contains the tests for loading agricultural use data. This includes the checks for correct loading of the tables, as well as the tests for the processing of the raw agricultural use data into weighted and compound based agricultural use percentages. All tests use the the data file `DataGroupsTests.mdb`. A description of the agricultural use data is provided in the validation data description document.

Test	Description	Outcome
AgriculturalUsesTestApple	Tests correct processing of agricultural uses for the food apple, and compounds A, B, C, and D. Tests the weighted agricultural use percentages per compound, per location and tests the aggregated (over all locations) weighted agricultural use percentage. UseAgriculturalUseTable = true, UseAgriculturalUsePercentage = true, SetMissingAgriculturalUseAsUnauthorized = true.	Passed
AgriculturalUsesTestAppleMissingAuthorized	Tests correct processing of agricultural uses for the food apple, and compounds A, B, C, and D. Tests the weighted agricultural use percentages per compound, per location and tests the aggregated (over all locations) weighted agricultural use percentage. UseAgriculturalUseTable = true, UseAgriculturalUsePercentage = true, SetMissingAgriculturalUseAsUnauthorized = false.	Passed
AgriculturalUsesTestBananas	Tests correct processing of agricultural uses for the food bananas, and compounds A, B, C, and D. Tests the weighted agricultural use percentages per compound, per location and tests the aggregated (over all locations) weighted agricultural use percentage. UseAgriculturalUseTable = true, UseAgriculturalUsePercentage = true, SetMissingAgriculturalUseAsUnauthorized = true.	Passed
AgriculturalUsesTestBananasMissingAuthorized	Tests correct processing of agricultural uses for the food bananas, and compounds A, B, C, and D. Tests the weighted agricultural use percentages per compound, per location and tests the aggregated (over all locations) weighted agricultural use percentage. UseAgriculturalUseTable = true, UseAgriculturalUsePercentage = true, SetMissingAgriculturalUseAsUnauthorized = false.	Passed
AgriculturalUsesTestPineapple	Tests correct processing of agricultural uses for the food pineapple, and compounds A, B, C, and D. Tests the weighted agricultural use percentages per compound, per location and tests the aggregated (over all locations) weighted agricultural use percentage. UseAgriculturalUseTable = true, UseAgriculturalUsePercentage = true, SetMissingAgriculturalUseAsUnauthorized = true.	Passed
AgriculturalUsesTestPineappleMissingAuthorized	Tests correct processing of agricultural uses for the food pineapple, and compounds A, B, C, and D. Tests the weighted agricultural use percentages per compound, per location and tests the aggregated (over all locations) weighted agricultural use percentage. UseAgriculturalUseTable = true, UseAgriculturalUsePercentage = true, SetMissingAgriculturalUseAsUnauthorized = false.	Passed
AgriculturalUsesTestWeightedUseGroupFractions	Tests the general weighted agricultural use fractions for each of the agricultural use groups for the foods apple, bananas, and pineapple. I.e., the weighted (location- aggregated) percentage of agricultural use	Passed

for the groups A, AB, and ABC. UseAgriculturalUseTable = true, UseAgriculturalUsePercentage = true, SetMissingAgriculturalUseAsUnauthorized = true.

CompoundsDataTests

Contains the tests for loading compounds data. All tests use the the data file DataGroupsTests.mdb. A description of the substance data is provided in the validation data description document.

Test	Description	Outcome
CompoundsDataTest1	Tests correct loading of the compounds. Validation check: assert that the expected compounds are present in the compounds of the compiled datasource and no other compounds exist in the compiled datasource.	Passed

ConcentrationsDataTests

This sections contains the tests for loading data from the concentrations data group. These tests are designed to test whether the concentration data is loaded correctly into the system, and the wrapper classes are constructed appropriately. All tests use the the data fileDataGroupsTests.mdb. A description of the concentration data is provided in the validation data description document.

Test	Description	Outcome
ConcentrationsDataTest2	Test correct loading of the analytical methods and the substance specific details of the analytical methods (analytical methods - compounds). Verification by counting the analytical methods (=5), and the number of samples per analytical method (AM1 = 5, AM2 = 5, AM3 = 1, AM4 = 3, and AM5 = 6).	Passed
ConcentrationsDataTest3	Test correct loading of the analytical methods and the substance specific details of the analytical methods (analytical methods - compounds). The analytical methods per compound (A = 5, B = 2, C = 2, D = 3).	Passed
ConcentrationsDataTest4	Test creation of sample compound records for the foods apple, pineapple, and bananas and the compounds A, B, C, and D. Verification by counting per food/compound combination, the number of missing values, non-detects, and positives.	Passed
ConcentrationsDataTest5	Test creation of compound residue collections for the foods apple, pineapple, and bananas and the compounds A, B, C, and D. Verification by checking per food/compound combination, the number of residues, the number of non-detects, the number of positives, and the fraction of positives.	Passed
ConcentrationsDataTest6	Test creation of compound residue collections through a sample compound record collection for the foods apple, pineapple, and bananas and the compounds A, B, C, and D. Verification by checking per food/compound combination, the number of residues, the number of non-detects, the number of positives, and the fraction of positives.	Passed
ConcentrationsDataTests1	Tests correct loading of the samples. Verification by counting the samples for the foods apple (=5), bananas (=5), and pineapple (=10) of the compiled datasource generated with the specified concentration data.	Passed

ConsumptionsDataTests

This sections contains the tests for loading data from the consumptions data group. These tests are designed to test whether the consumption data is loaded correctly into the system. This is done by generating a compiled data source based on the specified data source and performing the tests on the compiled data source. The compiled data source is generated from the raw data file DataGroupsTests.mdb. A description of the consumption data is provided in the validation data description document.

Test	Description	Outcome
ConsumptionsData_TestLoadConsumptions	Tests correct loading of the consumptions. Verification by counting the consumptions per food. Counts: apple (=17), bananas (=7), and pineapple (=3).	Passed

ConsumptionsData_TestLoadFoodSurveys	Tests correct loading of the food surveys. Verification by checking the expected food surveys of the compiled data source ("ValidationSurvey" and "EmptySurvey").	Passed
ConsumptionsData_TestLoadIndividualProperties	Tests correct loading of the individual properties. Verification by checking the co-factor and co-variate properties. Co-factors: "Age", "Gender", "ExtraCofactor", and "ExtraCovariate". Co-variate: "Age" and "ExtraCovariate".	Passed
ConsumptionsData_TestLoadIndividuals	Tests correct loading of the individuals. Verification by counting the individuals. Expected: 10 individuals.	Passed

EffectsDataTests

Contains the tests for loading effects data. All tests use the the data file DataGroupsTests.mdb. A description of the effects data is provided in thevalidation data description document.

Test	Description	Outcome
EffectsDataTest1	Tests correct loading of the effects. Validation check: assert that the expected effects are present in the effects of the compiled datasource and no other effects exist in the compiled datasource.	Passed
EffectsDataTest2	Tests correct loading of the relative potency factors. Validation check: assert that the expected compounds of the effect exist and no other compounds exist in the effects.	Passed

FoodEx2DataTests

This sections contains the tests for loading data from a data source in which the foods and consumptions are coded in FoodEx2 format. These tests are designed to test whether FoodEx2 coded data is loaded correctly into the system. All tests use the the data file FoodEx2Tests.mdb.

Test	Description	Outcome
FoodEx2DataTest_Foods	Tests correct loading of FoodEx2 coded foods.	Passed
FoodEx2DataTests_FoodHierarchy	<i>No description</i>	Passed

FoodsDataTests

This sections contains the tests for loading data from the foods data group. These tests are designed to test whether the foods data is loaded correctly into the system. All tests use the the data file DataGroupsTests.mdb. A description of the foods data is provided in the validation data description document.

Test	Description	Outcome
FoodsDataTest_FoodProperties	Tests correct loading of the food properties. Verification by checking the expected properties for the foods with properties (unit weight for the foods apple, bananas, and pineapple) and test for no properties on the other foods in the compiled datasource.	Passed
FoodsDataTest_Foods	Tests correct loading of the foods. Verification by making sure that only the expected foods are part of the foods of the compiled datasource.	Passed
FoodsDataTest_FoodTranslations	Tests correct loading of the food translations. Verification by checking that the expected translations exist in the compiled data source, and no other food translations exist.	Passed
FoodsDataTest_MarketShares	Tests correct loading of the food market shares. Verification by checking the that the expected market shares exist in the compiled datasource, and no other market shares exist.	Passed

MaximumResidueLimitsDataTests

Contains the tests for loading maximum residue llimits data. All tests use the the data file DataGroupsTests.mdb. A description of the maximum residue limits data is provided in the validation data description document.

Test	Description	Outcome
MaximumResidueLimitsDataTest1	Tests whether the maximum residue limits table is correctly loaded. Checks for each food and compound whether the expected MRL is present. Also checks	Passed

whether no other MRLs are loaded.

NonDietaryDataTests

This sections contains the tests for loading data from the non-dietary data group. These tests are designed to test whether the concentration data is loaded correctly into the system, and the wrapper classes are constructed appropriately. All tests use the the data fileDataGroupsTests.mdb. A description of the concentration data is provided in the validation data description document.

Test	Description	Outcome
NonDietaryDataTests1	Check the nominal non-dietary exposures of non-dietary survey 1 with unmatched individual exposures.	Passed
NonDietaryDataTests2	Check the nominal non-dietary exposures of non-dietary survey 2 with matched individual exposures.	Passed
NonDietaryDataTests3	Check the nominal non-dietary exposures of non-dietary survey 3 with matched individual exposures.	Passed

ProcessingFactorsDataTests

This sections contains the tests for loading data from the processing factors group. These tests are designed to test whether the processing factors data is loaded correctly into the system. All tests use the the data file DataGroupsTests.mdb. A description of the processing factors data is provided in the validation data description document.

Test	Description	Outcome
ProcessingFactorsDataTest1	Tests correct loading of the processing types. Verification by making sure that only the expected processing types exist in the compiled datasource. Check total count and assert presence of each of the processing types through the processing type code.	Passed
ProcessingFactorsDataTest2	Tests correct loading of the processing factors. Verification by making sure that only the expected processing factors exist in the compiled datasource. Check total count and assert presence of each of the processing types through the processing type code.	Passed

SSDConcentrationsTests

This sections contains the tests for loading concentration and compound data from and SSD file. These tests are designed to test whether this data is loaded correctly into the system. All tests use the the SSD data file SSDConcentrationsTestBase.mdb and uses a base data file for the other data groups SSDConcentrationsTestBase.mdb.

Test	Description	Outcome
TestSSDAnalyticalMethodCompounds	Tests correct loading of the substance information per analytical methods. Verification by counting the number of compounds per analytical method of the compiled datasource.	Passed
TestSSDAnalyticalMethods	Tests correct loading of the analytical methods. Verification by checking that only the expected analytical methods are part of the analytical methods of the compiled datasource.	Passed
TestSSDCompounds	Tests correct loading of the compounds. Verification by counting the compounds of the compiled datasource.	Passed
TestSSDConcentrations	Tests correct loading of the concentrations. Verification by checking the samples for food P0110010A and compound RF-0087-001-PPP, checking the number of positive concentrations and the total number of samples for this food/compound combination.	Passed
TestSSDSamples	Tests correct loading of the samples. Verification by counting the samples of the compiled datasource.	Passed

TabulatedConcentrationsDataTests

This sections contains the tests for loading tabulated concentration data. These tests are designed to test whether the concentration data is loaded correctly into the system, and the wrapper classes are constructed appropriately. All tests use the the data file DataGroupsTests.mdb. A description of the concentration data is provided in the validation data description document.

Test	Description	Outcome
TabulatedConcentrationsDataTest1	Test compound residue collections and sample compound collections generated for the food apple and the compounds A, B, C, and D. For the substance residue collections, validate the number of residues, the number of positives, and the number of non-detects. For the sample compound records, test the missing value counts.	Passed
TabulatedConcentrationsDataTest2	Test compound residue collections generated through the sample compound records for the food apple and the compounds A, B, C, and D.	Passed

UnitVariabilityFactorsDataTests

This sections contains the tests for loading data from the unit variability factors group. These tests are designed to test whether the unit variability factors data is loaded correctly into the system. All tests use the the data file DataGroupsTests.mdb. A description of the unit variability factors data is provided in the validation data description document.

Test	Description	Outcome
UnitVariabilityFactorsDataTest1	Tests correct loading of the unit variability factors by counting the number of unit variability factors loaded from the data and counting the unit variability factors linked to each food, compound and processingtype.	Passed
UnitVariabilityFactorsDataTest2	Tests correct loading of the unit variability factors. Tests correct values of the factor, coefficient, and units in composite sample fields.	Passed

SimulationInputDataTests

FocalFoodEatersTests

This section contains tests for validating that focal food eaters are correctly identified and filters on consumption days are correctly applied when gathering the simulation input data. All tests use the the data file DataGroupsTests.mdb.

Test	Description	Outcome
FocalFoodEatersTestsTest1	This test makes a food as measured subset selection on APPLE using ConsumerDaysOnly = true, and TreatFoodSubsetAsFocalFoodEatersConcept = true. Verify that with this option, also the other foods containing compound A are marked as food as measured when they are eaten by a person who has consumed APPLE. Verify that only the individuals that have consumed APPLE are included in the simulation input data.	Passed

FocalFoodsTests

This section contains the tests for validating the focal foods data input mechanism. It is tested using a base database, and a concentrations database (in tabulated form). All tests use the the base data file DataGroupsTests.mdb. All tests use the the focal foods data file TabulatedConcentrationsDataTests.mdb.

Test	Description	Outcome
FocalFoodsTest1	Replace the concentrations of for Apple with the concentrations from the focal foods database. Verify that for apple, the sample counts match those of the focal foods database for Apple, and that for the other foods, the counts match the concentrations of the base database.	Passed

IndividualSubsetSelectionTests

This section contains tests for validating that individual subset selections are processed correctly. All tests use the the data file SubsetSelectionTests.mdb.

Test	Description	Outcome
AllIndividualProperties	Test whether the properties that are defined for the	Passed

	individuals are loaded correctly.	Passed
CovariableIndividualProperties	Test whether the properties that are defined for the individuals are loaded correctly.	Passed
IndividualAgeGenderSubsetSelectionTest	Make age and gender subset definitions and verify that the counts of the selected individuals match the expected counts w.r.t. the specified subsets.	Passed
IndividualAgeSubsetSelectionTest1	Make an age subset definitions and verify that the counts of the selected individuals match the expected counts for the specified subsets. Test an age subset definition that yields an empty subset.	Passed
IndividualAgeSubsetSelectionTest2	Make an age subset definitions and verify that the counts of the selected individuals match the expected counts for the specified subsets. Test an age subset definition based on a non-empty interval.	Passed
IndividualAgeSubsetSelectionTest3	Make an age subset definitions and verify that the counts of the selected individuals match the expected counts for the specified subsets. Test an age subset definition based on a lower bound definition.	Passed
IndividualAgeSubsetSelectionTest4	Make an age subset definitions and verify that the counts of the selected individuals match the expected counts for the specified subset. Test an age subset definition based on an upper bound definition.	Passed
IndividualFoodAsEatenSubsetSelectionTest	Make a gender subset selection and verify that the foods as eaten and foods as measured don't include foods that are not consumed by the individuals of the subset. Verification by means of comparing counts of the foods as eaten/measured with the expected counts.	Passed
IndividualGenderSubsetSelectionTest1	Make a gender subset definition and verify that the counts of the selected individuals match the expected counts for the specified subset. Test the gender subset definition that yields an empty subset.	Passed
IndividualGenderSubsetSelectionTest2	Make a gender subset definition and verify that the counts of the selected individuals match the expected counts for the specified subset. Test the gender subset definition that yields all individuals.	Passed
IndividualGenderSubsetSelectionTest3	Make a gender subset definition and verify that the counts of the selected individuals match the expected counts for the specified subset. Test the gender subset definition for only the males.	Passed
IndividualGenderSubsetSelectionTest4	Make a gender subset definition and verify that the counts of the selected individuals match the expected counts for the specified subset. Test the gender subset definition for only the females.	Passed
IndividualSubsetSelectionNoSubset	Verify that the selected subset of individuals yields all individuals in case that there are no subsets.	Passed

A.2 EuroMix toolbox (MCRA 9) integration test results

In the following table, the integration test results are given from the EuroMix toolbox (MCRA version 9).

Test report: Integration Tests

This page is automatically generated and summarizes the results of the automated tests for validating the various parts of the system. The main emphasis of the automatic test written for MCRA lies on: testing the data and database integrity, functional testing of individual simulation components, functional testing of complete simulation runs, and load/performance testing of data load operations and complete

simulations.

Test date: 2019-04-04T11:06:41.5738796+02:00

ConceptsTests

DynamicMembersTest

Test	Description	Outcome
GetMembers1	<i>No description</i>	Passed

DynamicSectionsTest

Test	Description	Outcome
DynamicSectionsTest1	<i>No description</i>	Passed

EnumAttributesTest

Test	Description	Outcome
GetEnumDisplayAttributeTest	<i>No description</i>	Passed

JobExecuterTests

Test	Description	Outcome
RunConcentrationModellingTest	Creates a small test project with default settings and runs a complete simulation.	Passed
RunExposureScreeningTest	Creates a small test project with default settings and runs a complete simulation.	Passed
RunFoodConversionTest	Creates a small test project with default settings and runs a complete simulation.	Passed
RunIntakeCalculationTest	Creates a small test project with default settings and runs a complete simulation.	Passed
RunSimulationTest	Creates a small test project with default settings and runs a complete simulation.	Passed

ListsCapacityTests

Test	Description	Outcome
ListCapacityTest1	<i>No description</i>	Passed

ParallelPerformanceTests

Test	Description	Outcome
HardcoreParallelTest1	<i>No description</i>	Passed
HardcoreParallelTest2	<i>No description</i>	Passed
PerformanceTest1	<i>No description</i>	Passed

Initialization

DirectoryChecks

Test	Description	Outcome
RepositoryPathExistsTest	<i>No description</i>	Passed
TestDataPathExistsTest	<i>No description</i>	Passed

FileChecks

Test	Description	Outcome
CheckIfRepositoryIsAvailable	<i>No description</i>	Passed

IntegrationTests

This section contains integration tests, for validating the interaction between multiple parts of the system.

DataIntegrityTests

This section contains data integrity tests, for validating correct processing of input data.

AgriculturalUsesDataTests

This section contains the tests for loading agricultural use data. This includes the checks for correct loading of the tables, as well as the tests for the processing of the raw agricultural use data into weighted and substance based agricultural use percentages. All tests use the the data fileDataGroupsTests.mdb. A description of the agricultural use data is provided in the validation data description document.

Test	Description	Outcome
AgriculturalUsesTestApple	Tests correct processing of agricultural uses for the food apple, and substances A, B, C, and D. Tests the weighted agricultural use percentages per substance, per location and tests the aggregated (over all locations) weighted agricultural use percentage. UseAgriculturalUseTable = true, UseAgriculturalUsePercentage = true, SetMissingAgriculturalUseAsUnauthorized = true.	Passed
AgriculturalUsesTestAppleMissingAuthorized	Tests correct processing of agricultural uses for the food apple, and substances A, B, C, and D. Tests the weighted agricultural use percentages per substance, per location and tests the aggregated (over all locations) weighted agricultural use percentage. UseAgriculturalUseTable = true, UseAgriculturalUsePercentage = true, SetMissingAgriculturalUseAsUnauthorized = false.	Passed
AgriculturalUsesTestBananas	Tests correct processing of agricultural uses for the food bananas, and substances A, B, C, and D. Tests the weighted agricultural use percentages per substance, per location and tests the aggregated (over all locations) weighted agricultural use percentage. UseAgriculturalUseTable = true, UseAgriculturalUsePercentage = true, SetMissingAgriculturalUseAsUnauthorized = true.	Passed
AgriculturalUsesTestBananasMissingAuthorized	Tests correct processing of agricultural uses for the food bananas, and substances A, B, C, and D. Tests the weighted agricultural use percentages per substance, per location and tests the aggregated (over all locations) weighted agricultural use percentage. UseAgriculturalUseTable = true, UseAgriculturalUsePercentage = true, SetMissingAgriculturalUseAsUnauthorized = false.	Passed
AgriculturalUsesTestPineapple	Tests correct processing of agricultural uses for the food pineapple, and substances A, B, C, and D. Tests the weighted agricultural use percentages per	Passed

	substance, per location and tests the aggregated (over all locations) weighted agricultural use percentage. UseAgriculturalUseTable = true, UseAgriculturalUsePercentage = true, SetMissingAgriculturalUseAsUnauthorized = true.	
AgriculturalUsesTestPineappleMissingAuthorized	Tests correct processing of agricultural uses for the food pineapple, and substances A, B, C, and D. Tests the weighted agricultural use percentages per substance, per location and tests the aggregated (over all locations) weighted agricultural use percentage. UseAgriculturalUseTable = true, UseAgriculturalUsePercentage = true, SetMissingAgriculturalUseAsUnauthorized = false.	Passed
AgriculturalUsesTestWeightedUseGroupFractions	Tests the general weighted agricultural use fractions for each of the agricultural use groups for the foods apple, bananas, and pineapple. I.e., the weighted (location- aggregated) percentage of agricultural use for the groups A, AB, and ABC. UseAgriculturalUseTable = true, UseAgriculturalUsePercentage = true, SetMissingAgriculturalUseAsUnauthorized = true.	Passed

CompoundsDataTests

Contains the tests for loading compounds data. All tests use the the data file DataGroupsTests.mdb. A description of the substance data is provided in the validation data description document.

Test	Description	Outcome
CompoundsDataTest1	Tests correct loading of the substances. Validation check: assert that the expected compounds are present in the substances of the compiled datasource and no other compounds exist in the compiled datasource.	Passed

ConcentrationsDataTests

This sections contains the tests for loading data from the concentrations data group. These tests are designed to test whether the concentration data is loaded correctly into the system, and the wrapper classes are constructed appropriately. All tests use the the data fileDataGroupsTests.mdb. A description of the concentration data is provided in the validation data description document.

Test	Description	Outcome
ConcentrationsDataTest2	Test correct loading of the analytical methods and the substance specific details of the analytical methods (analytical methods - compounds). Verification by counting the analytical methods (=5), and the number of samples per analytical method (AM1 = 5, AM2 = 5, AM3 = 1, AM4 = 3, and AM5 = 6).	Passed
ConcentrationsDataTest3	Test correct loading of the analytical methods and the substance specific details of the analytical methods (analytical methods - compounds). The analytical methods per substance (A = 5, B = 2, C = 2, D = 3).	Passed
ConcentrationsDataTest4	Test creation of sample substance records for the foods apple, pineapple, and bananas and the substances A, B, C, and D. Verification by counting per food/substance combination, the number of missing values, non-detects, and positives.	Passed

ConcentrationsDataTest5	Test creation of substance residue collections for the foods apple, pineapple, and bananas and the substances A, B, C, and D. Verification by checking per food/substance combination, the number of residues, the number of non-detects, the number of positives, and the fraction of positives.	Passed
ConcentrationsDataTests1	Tests correct loading of the samples. Verification by counting the samples for the foods apple (=5), bananas (=5), and pineapple (=10) of the compiled datasource generated with the specified concentration data.	Passed

ConsumptionsDataTests

This sections contains the tests for loading data from the consumptions data group. These tests are designed to test whether the consumption data is loaded correctly into the system. This is done by generating a compiled data source based on the specified data source and performing the tests on the compiled data source. The compiled data source is generated from the raw data file DataGroupsTests.mdb. A description of the consumption data is provided in the validation data description document.

Test	Description	Outcome
ConsumptionsData_TestLoadConsumptions	Tests correct loading of the consumptions. Verification by counting the consumptions per food. Counts: apple (=17), bananas (=7), and pineapple (=3).	Passed
ConsumptionsData_TestLoadFoodSurveys	Tests correct loading of the food surveys. Verification by checking the expected food surveys of the compiled data source ("ValidationSurvey" and "EmptySurvey").	Passed
ConsumptionsData_TestLoadIndividualProperties	Tests correct loading of the individual properties. Verification by checking the co-factor and co-variate properties. Co-factors: "Age", "Gender", "ExtraCofactor", and "ExtraCovariable". Co-variate: "Age" and "ExtraCovariate".	Passed
ConsumptionsData_TestLoadIndividuals	Tests correct loading of the individuals. Verification by counting the individuals. Expected: 10 individuals.	Passed

EffectsDataTests

Contains the tests for loading effects data. All tests use the the data file DataGroupsTests.mdb. A description of the effects data is provided in the validation data description document.

Test	Description	Outcome
EffectsDataTest1	Tests correct loading of the effects. Validation check: assert that the expected effects are present in the effects of the compiled datasource and no other effects exist in the compiled datasource.	Passed
EffectsDataTest2	Tests correct loading of the relative potency factors. Validation check: assert that the expected compounds of the effect exist and no other compounds exist in the effects.	Passed

FoodEx2DataTests

This sections contains the tests for loading data from a data source in which the foods and consumptions are coded in FoodEx2 format. These tests are designed to test whether FoodEx2 coded data is loaded correctly into the system. All tests use the the data file FoodEx2Tests.mdb.

Test	Description	Outcome
FoodEx2DataTest_Foods	Tests correct loading of FoodEx2 coded foods.	Passed
FoodEx2DataTests_FoodHierarchy	<i>No description</i>	Passed

FoodsDataTests

This sections contains the tests for loading data from the foods data group. These tests are designed to test whether the foods data is loaded correctly into the system. All tests use the the data file DataGroupsTests.mdb. A description of the foods data is provided in the validation data description document.

Test	Description	Outcome
FoodsDataTest_FoodProperties	Tests correct loading of the food properties. Verification by checking the expected properties for the foods with properties (unit weight for the foods apple, bananas, and pineapple) and test for no properties on the other foods in the compiled datasource.	Passed
FoodsDataTest_Foods	Tests correct loading of the foods. Verification by making sure that only the expected foods are part of the foods of the compiled datasource.	Passed
FoodsDataTest_FoodTranslations	Tests correct loading of the food translations. Verification by checking that the expected translations exist in the compiled data source, and no other food translations exist.	Passed
FoodsDataTest_MarketShares	Tests correct loading of the food market shares. Verification by checking the that the expected market shares exist in the compiled datasource, and no other market shares exist.	Passed

MaximumResidueLimitsDataTests

Contains the tests for loading maximum residue llimits data. All tests use the the data file DataGroupsTests.mdb. A description of the maximum residue limits data is provided in the validation data description document.

Test	Description	Outcome
MaximumResidueLimitsDataTest1	Tests whether the maximum residue limits table is correctly loaded. Checks for each food and substance whether the expected MRL is present. Also checks whether no other MRLs are loaded.	Passed

NonDietaryDataTests

This sections contains the tests for loading data from the non-dietary data group. These tests are designed to test whether the concentration data is loaded correctly into the system, and the wrapper classes are constructed appropriately. All tests use the the data fileDataGroupsTests.mdb. A description of the concentration data is provided in the validation data description document.

Test	Description	Outcome
NonDietaryDataTests1	Check the nominal non-dietary exposures of non-dietary survey 1 with unmatched individual exposures.	Passed
NonDietaryDataTests2	Check the nominal non-dietary exposures of non-dietary survey 2 with matched individual exposures.	Passed

ProcessingFactorsDataTests

This sections contains the tests for loading data from the processing factors group. These tests are designed to test whether the processing factors data is loaded correctly into the system. All tests use the the data file DataGroupsTests.mdb. A description of the processing factors data is provided in the validation data description document.

Test	Description	Outcome
ProcessingFactorsDataTest1	Tests correct loading of the processing types. Verification by making sure that only the expected processing types exist in the compiled datasource. Check total count and assert presence of each of the processing types through the processing type code.	Passed
ProcessingFactorsDataTest2	Tests correct loading of the processing factors. Verification by making sure that only the expected processing factors exist in the compiled datasource. Check total count and assert presence of each of the processing types through the processing type code.	Passed

SSDConcentrationsTests

This sections contains the tests for loading concentration and substance data from and SSD file. These tests are designed to test whether this data is loaded correctly into the system. All tests use the the SSD data file SSDConcentrationsTestBase.mdb and uses a base data file for the other data groups SSDConcentrationsTestBase.mdb.

Test	Description	Outcome
TestSSDAnalyticalMethodCompounds	Tests correct loading of the substance information per analytical methods. Verification by counting the number of compounds per analytical method of the compiled datasource.	Passed
TestSSDAnalyticalMethods	Tests correct loading of the analytical methods. Verification by checking that only the expected analytical methods are part of the analytical methods of the compiled datasource.	Passed
TestSSDCompounds	Tests correct loading of the substances. Verification by counting the substances of the compiled datasource.	Passed
TestSSDConcentrations	Tests correct loading of the concentrations. Verification by checking the samples for food P0110010A and substance RF-0087-001-PPP, checking the number of positive concentrations and the total number of samples for this food/substance combination.	Passed
TestSSDSamples	Tests correct loading of the samples. Verification by counting the samples of the compiled datasource.	Passed

TabulatedConcentrationsDataTests

This sections contains the tests for loading tabulated concentration data. These tests are designed to test whether the concentration data is loaded correctly into the system, and the wrapper classes are constructed appropriately. All tests use the the data file DataGroupsTests.mdb. A description of the concentration data is provided in the validation data description document.

Test	Description	Outcome
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TabulatedConcentrationsDataTest1	Test substance residue collections and sample substance collections generated for the food apple and the substances A, B, C, and D. For the substance residue collections, validate the number of residues, the number of positives, and the number of non-detects. For the sample substance records, test the missing value counts.	Passed
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UnitVariabilityFactorsDataTests

This sections contains the tests for loading data from the unit variability factors group. These tests are designed to test whether the unit variability factors data is loaded correctly into the system. All tests use the the data file DataGroupsTests.mdb. A description of the unit variability factors data is provided in the validation data description document.

Test	Description	Outcome
UnitVariabilityFactorsDataTest1	Tests correct loading of the unit variability factors by counting the number of unit variability factors loaded from the data and counting the unit variability factors linked to each food, substance and processingtype.	Passed
UnitVariabilityFactorsDataTest2	Tests correct loading of the unit variability factors. Tests correct values of the factor, coefficient, and units in composite sample fields.	Passed

SimulationInputDataTests

FocalFoodEatersTests

This section contains tests for validating that focal food eaters are correctly identified and filters on consumption days are correctly applied when gathering the simulation input data. All tests use the the data file DataGroupsTests.mdb.

Test	Description	Outcome
FocalFoodEatersTest1	This test makes a food as measured subset selection on APPLE using ConsumerDaysOnly = true, and TreatFoodSubsetAsFocalFoodEatersConcept = true. Verify that with this option, also the other foods containing substance A are marked as food as measured when they are eaten by a person who has consumed APPLE. Verify that only the individuals that have consumed APPLE are included in the simulation input data.	Passed

FocalFoodsTests

This section contains the tests for validating the focal foods data input mechanism. It is tested using a base database, and a concentrations database (in tabulated form). All tests use the the base data file DataGroupsTests.mdb. All tests use the the focal foods data file TabulatedConcentrationsDataTests.mdb.

Test	Description	Outcome
FocalFoodsTest1	Replace the concentrations of for Apple with the concentrations from the focal foods database. Verify that for apple, the sample counts match those of the focal foods database for Apple, and that for the other foods, the counts match the concentrations of the base database.	Passed

IndividualSubsetSelectionTests

This section contains tests for validating that individual subset selections are processed correctly. All tests use the the data file SubsetSelectionTests.mdb.

Test	Description	Outcome
AllIndividualProperties	Test whether the properties that are defined for the individuals are loaded correctly.	Passed
CovariableIndividualProperties	Test whether the properties that are defined for the individuals are loaded correctly.	Passed
IndividualAgeGenderSubsetSelectionTest	Make age and gender subset definitions and verify that the counts of the selected individuals match the expected counts w.r.t. the specified subsets.	Passed
IndividualAgeSubsetSelectionTest1	Make an age subset definitions and verify that the counts of the selected individuals match the expected counts for the specified subsets. Test an age subset definition that yields an empty subset.	Passed
IndividualAgeSubsetSelectionTest2	Make an age subset definitions and verify that the counts of the selected individuals match the expected counts for the specified subsets. Test an age subset definition based on a non-empty interval.	Passed
IndividualAgeSubsetSelectionTest3	Make an age subset definitions and verify that the counts of the selected individuals match the expected counts for the specified subsets. Test an age subset definition based on a lower bound definition.	Passed
IndividualAgeSubsetSelectionTest4	Make an age subset definitions and verify that the counts of the selected individuals match the expected counts for the specified subset. Test an age subset definition based on an upper bound definition.	Passed
IndividualFoodAsEatenSubsetSelectionTest	Make a gender subset selection and verify that the foods as eaten and foods as measured don't include foods that are not consumed by the individuals of the subset. Verification by means of comparing counts of the foods as eaten/measured with the expected counts.	Passed
IndividualGenderSubsetSelectionTest1	Make a gender subset definition and verify that the counts of the selected individuals match the expected counts for the specified subset. Test the gender subset definition that yields an empty subset.	Passed
IndividualGenderSubsetSelectionTest2	Make a gender subset definition and verify that the counts of the selected individuals match the expected counts for the specified subset. Test the gender subset definition that yields all individuals.	Passed
IndividualGenderSubsetSelectionTest3	Make a gender subset definition and verify that the counts of the selected individuals match the expected counts for the specified subset. Test the gender subset definition for only the males.	Passed
IndividualGenderSubsetSelectionTest4	Make a gender subset definition and verify that the counts of the selected individuals match the expected counts for the specified subset. Test the gender subset definition for only the females.	Passed
IndividualSubsetSelectionNoSubset	Verify that the selected subset of individuals yields all individuals in case that there are no subsets.	Passed

SqlServerReaderDataTests

ConsumptionsDataTests

Test	Description	Outcome
ReadWriteCompiledDatasourceDataToCsvFilesTest	ReadWriteCompiledDatasourceDataTest	Passed
ReadWriteCompiledDatasourceDataToZipTest	ReadWriteCompiledDatasourceDataTest	Passed

A.3 Regression tests

A.3.1 Validation test 1: Acute cumulative exposure assessment with generated data

Acute, short term cumulative exposure assessment.

Settings

Data	
Single data-source	gen-2-100-2+100-40-5+10-20-10.zip
Select	
Food consumption survey	survey
Cumulative assessment group	Effect
Substances	20 substances in assessment group
Reference substance	cmp0
Model	
Exposure calculation tier	EFSA Guidance Optimistic
Number of Monte Carlo simulations	10000
Uncertainty analysis	No

Results

This table shows the calculated exposure for each percentile. The table shows no units because the values are only used to compare the outcomes of the algorithms and don't represent any real-world values.

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	13.721	13.68	1.00
90	67.83	67.689	1.00
95	96.424	97.243	0.99
99	159.04	160.51	0.99
99.9	266.23	265.5	1.00
99.99	274.01	273.16	1.00

A.3.2 Validation test 2: Acute custom cumulative exposure assessment

Acute, short term cumulative exposure assessment.

Settings

Data	
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Foods	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Substances	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Consumptions	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Concentrations	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Processing	TriazolesProcessing-Optimistic.mdb
Unit variability	UnitVariability.mdb
Effects	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Select	
Food consumption survey	DNFCS_2003
Cumulative assessment group	Hepatotoxicity
Substances	11 substances in assessment group
Reference substance	Flusilazole
Model	
Exposure calculation tier	Custom
Dietary exposures method	Distribution estimates
Concentration model	Empirical, nondetects set to zero. fixed processing factors.
Number of Monte Carlo simulations	10000
Uncertainty analysis	10 resample cycles, 1000 MC simulations

Results

This table shows the calculated exposure for each percentile. The resulting values for this project are identical.

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	0.00037348	0.00037348	1.00
90	0.012905	0.012905	1.00
95	0.03166	0.03166	1.00
99	0.12328	0.12328	1.00
99.9	0.55654	0.55654	1.00
99.99	1.5527	1.5527	1.00

A.3.3 Validation test 3: Acute cumulative exposure assessment

Acute, short term cumulative exposure assessment.

Settings

Data	
Foods	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Substances	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Consumptions	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Concentrations	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Processing	TriazolesProcessing-Optimistic.mdb
Unit variability	UnitVariability.mdb
Effects	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Select	

Food consumption survey	DNFCS_2003
Cumulative assessment group	Hepatotoxicity
Substances	11 substances in assessment group
Reference substance	Flusilazole
Model	
Exposure calculation tier	EFSA Guidance Optimistic
Number of Monte Carlo simulations	10000
Uncertainty analysis	10 resample cycles, 1000 MC simulations

Results

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	0.64486	0.63917	1.01
90	1.7125	1.7171	1.00
95	2.2261	2.2365	1.00
99	3.8093	3.874	0.98
99.9	7.2025	7.4156	0.97
99.99	12.362	12.468	0.99

A.3.4 Validation test 4: Chronic cumulative exposure assessment

Chronic, long term cumulative exposure assessment.

Settings

Data	
Foods	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Substances	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Consumptions	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Concentrations	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Processing	TriazolesProcessing-Optimistic.mdb
Unit variability	UnitVariability.mdb
Effects	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Select	
Food consumption survey	DNFCS_2003
Cumulative assessment group	Cranio-facial effect
Substances	Bitertanol, Cyproconazole, Diniconazole, Epoxiconazole, Flusilazole, Propiconazole, Triadimefon
Reference substance	Cyproconazole
Model	
Exposure calculation tier	Custom
Dietary exposures method	Distribution estimates
Exposure model-type	BetaBinomial Normal
Concentration model	Empirical, nondetects set to zero. fixed processing factors.
Number of Monte Carlo simulations	10000
Uncertainty analysis	10 resample cycles, 1000 MC simulations

Results

Results for dietary exposures distribution, model based

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	0.018653	0.018557	1.01
90	0.058856	0.060002	0.98
95	0.081035	0.083881	0.97
99	0.14672	0.15651	0.94
99.9	0.27764	0.29456	0.94
99.99	0.367	0.48827	0.75

Differences in percentiles in 'model based' percentiles are the result of code changes which have altered the propagation of random seeding. Running the project with different seeds gives the same variance in resulting percentiles with the same version of MCRA.

Results for dietary exposures distribution, model assisted

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	0.020554	0.020554	1.00
90	0.056727	0.056727	1.00
95	0.068271	0.068271	1.00
99	0.10787	0.10787	1.00
99.9	0.23272	0.23272	1.00
99.99	0.32809	0.32809	1.00

A.3.5 Validation test 5: Chronic cumulative exposure assessment

Chronic, long term cumulative exposure assessment.

Settings

Data	
Foods	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Substances	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Consumptions	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Concentrations	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Processing	TriazolesProcessing-Optimistic.mdb
Unit variability	UnitVariability.mdb
Effects	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Select	
Food consumption survey	DNFCS_2003
Cumulative assessment group	Cranio-facial effect
Substances	Bitertanol, Cyproconazole, Diniconazole, Epoxiconazole, Flusilazole, Propiconazole, Triadimefon
Reference substance	Cyproconazole
Model	
Exposure calculation tier	EFSA Guidance Optimistic

Number of Monte Carlo simulations	10000
Uncertainty analysis	10 resample cycles, 1000 MC simulations

Results

Results for dietary exposures distribution, model based

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	0.98997	0.98574	1.00
90	1.767	1.7889	0.99
95	2.1117	2.0818	1.01
99	2.8835	2.8593	1.01
99.9	3.8449	4.436	0.87
99.99	4.6398	6.5017	0.71

Differences in percentiles in 'model based' percentiles are the result of code changes which have altered the propagation of random seeding. Running the project with different seeds gives the same variance in resulting percentiles with the same version of MCRA.

Results for dietary exposures distribution, model assisted

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	1.0369	1.0369	1.00
90	1.6109	1.6109	1.00
95	1.8012	1.8012	1.00
99	2.2627	2.2627	1.00
99.9	3.3834	3.3834	1.00
99.99	3.7228	3.7228	1.00

A.3.6 Validation test 6: Chronic TDS (total diet study) exposure assessment

TDS Chronic, long term exposure assessment.

Settings

Data	
Single data-source	TDS data 1.mdb
Select	
Food consumption survey	FTDS2
Substance	DON
Model	
Exposure calculation tier	Custom
Dietary exposures method	Distribution estimates
Exposure model-type	BetaBinomial Normal
Concentration model	Summary statistics, nondetects set to zero. fixed processing factors.
Uncertainty analysis	10 resample cycles, 1000 MC simulations

Results

Results for dietary exposures distribution, model based

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	446.49	447.35	1.00
90	975.8	968.56	1.01
95	1218.9	1215.5	1.00
99	1753.9	1806.5	0.97
99.9	3031.7	2761.3	1.10
99.99	4677.8	3340.1	1.40

Differences in percentiles in 'model based' percentiles are the result of code changes which have altered the propagation of random seeding. Running the project with different seeds gives the same variance in resulting percentiles with the same version of MCRA.

Results for dietary exposures distribution, model assisted

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	501.4	501.4	1.00
90	910.45	910.45	1.00
95	1044.5	1044.5	1.00
99	1374.5	1374.5	1.00
99.9	2028	2028	1.00
99.99	2738.9	2738.9	1.00

A.3.7 Validation test 7: Acute cumulative aggregate exposure assessment

Acute, short term cumulative aggregate exposure assessment.

Settings

Data	
Foods	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Substances	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Consumptions	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Concentrations	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Effects	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Non-dietary	NetherlandsTriazoles_NonDietaryAdultConsExpo.mdb
Select	
Food consumption survey	DNFCS_2003
Cumulative assessment group	Hepatotoxicity
Substances	11 substances in assessment group
Reference substance	Flusilazole
Model	
Exposure calculation tier	Custom
Dietary exposures method	Distribution estimates
Concentration model	Empirical, nondetects set to zero. fixed processing factors.
Aggregate exposure	oral absorption factor for dietary exposure = 1
Number of Monte Carlo simulations	10000
Uncertainty analysis	No

Results

Results for dietary exposure distribution (daily intakes)

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	0.00041638	0.00041638	1.00
90	0.014244	0.014244	1.00
95	0.03475	0.03475	1.00
99	0.16715	0.16715	1.00
99.9	0.8742	0.8742	1.00
99.99	2.1728	2.1728	1.00

A.3.8 Validation test 8: Acute cumulative exposure assessment, pessimistic

Acute, short term cumulative exposure assessment

Settings

Data	
Foods	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Substances	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Consumptions	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Concentrations	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Processing	TriazolesProcessing-Optimistic.mdb
Unit variability	UnitVariability.mdb
Effects	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Select	
Food consumption survey	DNFCS_2003
Cumulative assessment group	Hepatotoxicity
Substances	11 substances in assessment group
Reference substance	Flusilazole
Model	
Exposure calculation tier	EFSA Guidance Pessimistic
Number of Monte Carlo simulations	10000
Uncertainty analysis	10 resample cycles, 1000 MC simulations

Results

Results for dietary exposure distribution (daily intakes)

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	0.64486	0.63917	1.01
90	1.7125	1.7171	1.00
95	2.2261	2.2365	1.00
99	3.8093	3.874	0.98
99.9	7.2025	7.4156	0.97
99.99	12.362	12.468	0.99

A.3.9 Validation test 9: Chronic cumulative exposure assessment, pessimistic

Chronic, long term cumulative exposure assessment.

Settings

Data	
Foods	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Substances	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Consumptions	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Concentrations	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Processing	TriazolesProcessing-Optimistic.mdb
Unit variability	UnitVariability.mdb
Effects	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Select	
Food consumption survey	DNFCS_2003
Cumulative assessment group	Cranio-facial effect
Substances	Bitertanol, Cyproconazole, Diniconazole, Epoxiconazole, Flusilazole, Propiconazole, Triadimefon
Reference substance	Cyproconazole
Model	
Exposure calculation tier	EFSA Guidance Pessimistic
Number of Monte Carlo simulations	10000
Uncertainty analysis	10 resample cycles, 1000 MC simulations

Results

Results for dietary exposures distribution, model based

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	0.98929	0.98507	1.00
90	1.7658	1.7877	0.99
95	2.1103	2.0804	1.01
99	2.8816	2.8574	1.01
99.9	3.8423	4.4331	0.87
99.99	4.6367	6.4975	0.71

Differences in percentiles in 'model based' percentiles are the result of code changes which have altered the propagation of random seeding. Running the project with different seeds gives the same variance in resulting percentiles with the same version of MCRA.

Results for dietary exposures distribution, model assisted

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	1.0365	1.0365	1.00
90	1.6077	1.6077	1.00
95	1.801	1.801	1.00
99	2.2608	2.2608	1.00

99.9	3.371	3.371	1.00
99.99	3.6956	3.6956	1.00

A.3.10 Validation test 10: Acute cumulative exposure assessment, optimistic

Acute, short term. cumulative exposure assessment

Settings

Data	
Foods	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Substances	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Consumptions	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Concentrations	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Processing	TriazolesProcessing-Optimistic.mdb
Unit variability	UnitVariability.mdb
Effects	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Select	
Food consumption survey	DNFCS_2003
Cumulative assessment group	Cranio-facial effect
Substances	Bitertanol, Cyproconazole, Diniconazole, Epoxiconazole, Flusilazole, Propiconazole, Triadimefon
Reference substance	Cyproconazole
Model	
Exposure calculation tier	EFSA Guidance Optimistic
Screening on	p95, 95% inclusion, nondetects replaced by 0 LOR
Mixture selection	Exposures are risk based: mixtures k = 4, sparseness 0.20, iterations 1000
Number of Monte Carlo simulations	50000
Uncertainty analysis	10 resample cycles, 10000 MC simulations

Results

Dietary exposure distribution (daily intakes).

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	0	0	-
90	0.014033	0.014033	1.00
95	0.053023	0.053023	1.00
99	0.2625	0.2625	1.00
99.9	1.0466	1.0466	1.00
99.99	3.0408	3.0408	1.00

A.3.11 Validation test 11: Acute cumulative exposure assessment with focal commodity

Acute, short term cumulative exposure assessment with focal commodity.

Settings

Data	
Foods	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Substances	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Consumptions	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Concentrations	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Processing	TriazolesProcessing-Optimistic.mdb
Unit variability	UnitVariability.mdb
Effects	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Focal food samples	CyprusTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Select	
Food consumption survey	DNFCS_2003
Cumulative assessment group	Cranio-facial effect
Substances	Bitertanol, Cyproconazole, Diniconazole, Epoxiconazole, Flusilazole, Propiconazole, Triadimefon
Reference substance	Cyproconazole
Focal Foods	POTATOES
Model	
Exposure calculation tier	EFSA Guidance Optimistic
Screening on	p95, 95% inclusion, nondetects replaced by 0 LOR
Mixture selection	Exposures are risk based: mixtures k = 4, sparseness 0.20, iterations 1000
Number of Monte Carlo simulations	50000
Uncertainty analysis	10 resample cycles, 10000 MC simulations

Results

Dietary exposure distribution (daily intakes).

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	0	0	-
90	0.014033	0.014033	1.00
95	0.053023	0.053023	1.00
99	0.2625	0.2625	1.00
99.9	1.0466	1.0466	1.00
99.99	3.0408	3.0408	1.00

A.3.12 Validation test 12: Acute cumulative exposure assessment

Acute, short term. cumulative exposure assessment

Settings

Data	
Foods	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Substances	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Consumptions	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Concentrations	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb

Processing	TriazolesProcessing-Pessimistic.mdb
Unit variability	UnitVariability.mdb
Effects	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Select	
Food consumption survey	DNFCS_2003
Cumulative assessment group	Cranio-facial effect
Substances	Bitertanol, Cyproconazole, Diniconazole, Epoxiconazole, Flusilazole, Propiconazole, Triadimefon
Reference substance	Cyproconazole
Model	
Exposure calculation tier	EFSA Guidance Pessimistic
Screening on	p95, 95% inclusion, nondetects replaced by 1 LOR
Mixture selection	Exposures are risk based: mixtures k = 4, sparseness 0.20, iterations 1000
Number of Monte Carlo simulations	50000
Uncertainty analysis	10 resample cycles, 10000 MC simulations

Results

Dietary exposure distribution (daily intakes) percentiles.

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	0.84701	0.84528	1.00
90	2.2336	2.2431	1.00
95	2.9354	2.9531	0.99
99	5.0578	5.0745	1.00
99.9	9.8644	9.7426	1.01
99.99	16.006	16.225	0.99

A.3.13 Validation test 13: Acute cumulative health impact, hazard (ipra) assessment

Acute, short term. cumulative health impact, hazard (ipra) assessment

Settings

Data	
Foods	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Substances	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Consumptions	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Concentrations	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Effects	Steatosis Triazoles - NOAEL only.xlsx
Select	
Food consumption survey	DNFCS_2003
Effect	Liver steatosis
Substances	Bitertanol, Cyproconazole, Difenoconazole, Epoxiconazole, Flusilazole, Myclobutanil, Propiconazole, Tebuconazole
Reference substance	Cyproconazole

Model	
Exposure calculation tier	Custom
Dietary exposures method	Distribution estimates
Screening on	p95, 95% inclusion, nondetects replaced by 1 LOR
Concentration model	EFSA Guidance Pessimistic
Number of Monte Carlo simulations	5000
Uncertainty analysis	10 resample cycles, 5000 MC simulations

Results

Dietary exposure distribution (daily intakes) percentiles.

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	1.3396	1.3396	1.00
90	3.3861	3.3861	1.00
95	4.3126	4.3126	1.00
99	7.4985	7.4985	1.00
99.9	12.767	12.767	1.00
99.99	19.709	19.709	1.00

A.3.14 Validation test 14: Acute pessimistic cumulative exposure assessment

Acute, short term cumulative exposure assessment.

Settings

Data	
Foods	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Substances	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Consumptions	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Concentrations	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Processing	TriazolesProcessing-Pessimistic.mdb
Unit variability	UnitVariability.mdb
Effects	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Select	
Food consumption survey	DNFCS_2003
Cumulative assessment group	Cranio-facial effect
Substances	Bitertanol, Cyproconazole, Diniconazole, Epoxiconazole, Flusilazole, Propiconazole, Triadimefon
Reference substance	Cyproconazole
Model	
Exposure calculation tier	EFSA Guidance Pessimistic
Screening on	p95, 95% inclusion, nondetects replaced by 1 LOR
Mixture selection	Exposures are risk based: mixtures k = 4, sparseness 0.20, iterations 1000
Number of Monte Carlo simulations	50000
Uncertainty analysis	10 resample cycles, 10000 MC simulations

Results

Dietary exposure distribution (daily intakes) percentiles.

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	0.88123	0.87925	1.00
90	2.2027	2.21	1.00
95	2.8692	2.8704	1.00
99	4.7097	4.6814	1.01
99.9	8.2637	8.7536	0.94
99.99	15.999	15.999	1.00

A.3.15 Validation test 15: Acute, short term exposure assessment, FoodEx2

Acute, short term exposure assessment.

Settings

Data	
Foods	FoodCodesFoodEx2.mdb
Substances	NitraatConcentrationsSSDFoodEx2NoFacets.xlsx
Consumptions	VCP-BasisConsumptionsFoodex2.mdb
Concentrations	NitraatConcentrationsSSDFoodEx2NoFacets.xlsx
Select	
Food consumption survey	VCP-basis
Model	
Exposure calculation tier	Custom
Dietary exposures method	Distribution estimates
Concentration model	Empirical, nondetects set to zero. fixed processing factors.
Number of Monte Carlo simulations	100000
Uncertainty analysis	10 resample cycles, 10000 MC simulations,

Results

Dietary exposure distribution (daily intakes).

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	622.73	622.73	1.00
90	1840.3	1840.3	1.00
95	3092.3	3092.3	1.00
99	7137	7137	1.00
99.9	15933	15933	1.00
99.99	27689	27689	1.00

A.3.16 Validation test 16: Acute exposure assessment, optimistic.

Acute, short term exposure assessment, optimistic.

Settings

Data	
Single data-source	ValidationMCRA7.mdb
Select	
Food consumption survey	DNFCS-3
Substance	CAPTAN
Model	
Exposure calculation tier	EFSA Guidance Optimistic
Number of Monte Carlo simulations	100000
Uncertainty analysis	10 resample cycles, 10000 MC simulations

Results

Dietary exposure distribution (daily intakes).

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	0	0	-
90	0.097637	0.097637	1.00
95	0.432	0.432	1.00
99	4.0104	4.0104	1.00
99.9	24.043	24.043	1.00
99.99	71.887	71.887	1.00

A.3.17 Validation test 17: Acute exposure assessment, pessimistic.

Acute, short term exposure assessment, pessimistic.

Settings

Data	
Single data-source	ValidationMCRA7.mdb
Select	
Food consumption survey	DNFCS-3
Substance	CAPTAN
Model	
Exposure calculation tier	EFSA Guidance Pessimistic
Number of Monte Carlo simulations	100000
Uncertainty analysis	10 resample cycles, 10000 MC simulations

Results

Dietary exposure distribution (daily intakes).

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	0.0023599	0.0023599	1.00
90	0.19774	0.19774	1.00
95	0.59156	0.59156	1.00
99	4.1809	4.1809	1.00
99.9	26.293	26.293	1.00
99.99	101.73	101.73	1.00

A.3.18 Validation test 18: Chronic cumulative exposure assessment, optimistic
Chronic, long term cumulative exposure assessment, EFSA Guidance Optimistic.

Settings

Data	
Foods	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Substances	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Consumptions	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Concentrations	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Processing	TriazolesProcessing-Pessimistic.mdb
Effects	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Select	
Food consumption survey	DNFCS_2003
Cumulative assessment group	Hepatotoxicity
Substances	11 substances in assessment group
Reference substance	Cyproconazole
Model	
Exposure calculation tier	EFSA Guidance Optimistic
Screening on	p95, 95% inclusion, nondetects replaced by 0 LOR
Uncertainty analysis	10 resample cycles

Results

Dietary exposure distribution (Observed individual means), percentiles.

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	0.013977	0.013977	1.00
90	0.066364	0.066364	1.00
95	0.096306	0.096306	1.00
99	0.22621	0.22621	1.00
99.9	0.83545	0.83545	1.00
99.99	1.5364	1.5364	1.00

A.3.19 Validation test 19: Chronic cumulative exposure assessment 'apple' subset

Acute, short term. cumulative exposure assessment, restrict population on food as measured subset 'Apple', EFSA Guidance Optimistic.

Settings

Same as in A.3.18, with food as measured subset to restrict population on 'APPLE'.

Results

Dietary exposure distribution (Observed individual means), percentiles.

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	0.015966	0.015966	1.00
90	0.077764	0.077764	1.00
95	0.11518	0.11518	1.00
99	0.25222	0.25222	1.00
99.9	1.0244	1.0244	1.00
99.99	1.5553	1.5553	1.00

A.3.20 Validation test 20: Chronic cumulative exposure assessment 'dates' subset

Acute, short term. cumulative exposure assessment, restrict population on food as measured subset 'Dates', EFSA Guidance Optimistic.

Settings

Same as in A.3.18, with food as measured subset to restrict population on 'DATES'.

Results

Dietary exposure distribution (Observed individual means), percentiles.

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	0.025606	0.025606	1.00
90	0.083445	0.083445	1.00
95	0.091593	0.091593	1.00
99	0.11898	0.11898	1.00
99.9	0.13731	0.13731	1.00
99.99	0.13915	0.13915	1.00

A.3.21 Validation test 21: Chronic cumulative exposure assessment, pessimistic

Chronic, long term cumulative exposure assessment, EFSA Guidance Pessimistic.

Settings

Data	
Foods	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Substances	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Consumptions	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Concentrations	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Processing	TriazolesProcessing-Pessimistic.mdb
Effects	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Select	

Food consumption survey	DNFCS_2003
Cumulative assessment group	Hepatotoxicity
Substances	11 substances in assessment group
Reference substance	Cyproconazole
Model	
Exposure calculation tier	EFSA Guidance Pessimistic
Screening on	p95 , 95% inclusion, nondetects replaced by 1 LOR
Uncertainty analysis	10 resample cycles

Results

Dietary exposure distribution (daily intakes).

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	3.166	3.166	1.00
90	5.7989	5.7989	1.00
95	6.8431	6.8431	1.00
99	8.9832	8.9832	1.00
99.9	15.097	15.097	1.00
99.99	16.266	16.266	1.00

A.3.22 Validation test 22: Chronic cumulative exposure assessment, pessimistic, F20-25
Chronic, long term cumulative exposure assessment, EFSA Guidance Pessimistic on females between the age of 20 – 25 years.

Settings

Same as in A.3.21, with population subset on female individuals between 20 and 25 years of age.

Results

Dietary exposure distribution (daily intakes).

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	3.0598	3.0598	1.00
90	6.021	6.021	1.00
95	6.9207	6.9207	1.00
99	8.3368	8.3368	1.00
99.9	13.951	13.951	1.00
99.99	14.486	14.486	1.00

A.3.23 Validation test 23: Chronic cumulative health impact, hazard (ipra) assessment
Chronic cumulative health impact, hazard (ipra) assessment

Settings

Data	
Foods	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb

Substances	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Consumptions	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Concentrations	NetherlandsTriazoles2007-10.mdb
Effects	Steatosis Triazoles - NOAEL only.xlsx
Select	
Food consumption survey	DNFCS_2003
Effect	Liver steatosis
Substances	Bitertanol, Cyproconazole, Difenoconazole, Epoxiconazole, Flusilazole, Myclobutanil, Propiconazole, Tebuconazole
Reference substance	Cyproconazole
Model	
Exposure calculation tier	EFSA Guidance Pessimistic
Screening on	p95, 95% inclusion, nondetects replaced by 1 LOR
Uncertainty analysis	10 resample cycles

Results

Dietary exposure distribution (daily intakes).

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	1.4858	1.4858	1.00
90	2.7419	2.7419	1.00
95	3.2161	3.2161	1.00
99	4.1885	4.1885	1.00
99.9	6.7904	6.7904	1.00
99.99	6.9811	6.9811	1.00

A.3.24 Validation test 24: Chronic cumulative exposure assessment, pessimistic, M20-25

Chronic, long term cumulative exposure assessment, EFSA Guidance Pessimistic on males between the age of 20 – 25 years.

Settings

Same as in A.3.21, with population subset on male individuals between 20 and 25 years of age.

Results

Dietary exposure distribution (Observed individual means), percentiles.

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	3.3628	3.3628	1.00
90	5.7267	5.7267	1.00
95	6.5623	6.5623	1.00
99	7.3476	7.3476	1.00
99.9	8.7544	8.7544	1.00
99.99	8.943	8.943	1.00

A.3.25 Validation test 25: Chronic exposure assessment

Chronic, long term exposure assessment.

Settings

Data	
Foods	FoodCodesFoodEx2.mdb
Substances	NitraatConcentrationsSSDFoodEx2NoFacets.xlsx
Consumptions	VCP-BasisConsumptionsFoodex2.mdb
Concentrations	NitraatConcentrationsSSDFoodEx2NoFacets.xlsx
Select	
Food consumption survey	VCP-basis
Model	
Exposure calculation tier	Custom
Dietary exposures method	Distribution estimates
Exposure model-type	Observed Individual Means
Concentration model	Empirical, nondetects set to zero. fixed processing factors.
Uncertainty analysis	10 resample cycles

Results

Dietary exposure distribution (Observed individual means), percentiles.

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	697.91	697.91	1.00
90	2001.4	2001.4	1.00
95	2835.5	2835.5	1.00
99	4918.5	4918.5	1.00
99.9	9535.6	9535.6	1.00
99.99	14012	14012	1.00

A.3.26 Validation test 26: Chronic exposure assessment, Betabinomial normal model

Chronic, long term. exposure assessment

Settings

Data	
Single data-source	ValidationMCRA7.mdb
Select	
Food consumption survey	DNFCS-3
Substance	CAPTAN
Model	
Exposure calculation tier	Custom
Dietary exposures method	Distribution estimates
Exposure model-type	BetaBinomial Normal
Concentration model	Empirical, nondetects set to zero. fixed processing factors.

Number of Monte Carlo simulations	100000
Uncertainty analysis	10 resample cycles, 10000 MC simulations

Results

Results for dietary exposures distribution, model based

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	0.030976	0.030645	1.01
90	0.46841	0.47454	0.99
95	0.95259	0.9383	1.02
99	3.3632	3.2816	1.02
99.9	13.005	11.475	1.13
99.99	40.435	38.96	1.04

Differences in percentiles in 'model based' percentiles are the result of code changes which have altered the propagation of random seeding. Running the project with different seeds gives the same variance in resulting percentiles with the same version of MCRA.

Results for dietary exposures distribution, model assisted

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	0.040205	0.040205	1.00
90	0.50535	0.50535	1.00
95	0.96746	0.96746	1.00
99	4.0042	4.0042	1.00
99.9	10.421	10.421	1.00
99.99	15.699	15.699	1.00

A.3.27 Validation test 27: Chronic exposure assessment, model ISUF

Chronic, long term exposure assessment, Iowa State University Foods model.

Settings

Data	
Single data-source	ValidationMCRA7.mdb
Select	
Food consumption survey	DNFCS-3
Substance	CAPTAN
Model	
Exposure calculation tier	Custom
Dietary exposures method	Distribution estimates
Exposure model-type	Iowa State University Foods model
Concentration model	Empirical, nondetects set to zero. fixed processing factors.
Uncertainty analysis	10 resample cycles, 10000 MC simulations

Results

Distribution (ISUF), percentiles.

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	0.016164	0.016164	1.00
90	0.27166	0.27166	1.00
95	0.53955	0.53955	1.00
99	1.8281	1.8281	1.00
99.9	7.0273	7.0273	1.00
99.99	13.234	13.234	1.00

A.3.28 Validation test 28: Chronic exposure assessment, model LNN with correlation

Chronic, long term exposure assessment, LNN with correlation.

Settings

Data	
Single data-source	ValidationMCRA7.mdb
Select	
Food consumption survey	DNFCS-3
Substance	CAPTAN
Model	
Exposure calculation tier	Custom
Dietary exposures method	Distribution estimates
Exposure model-type	Logistic-Normal Normal with correlation
Concentration model	Empirical, nondetects set to zero. fixed processing factors.
Number of Monte Carlo simulations	100000
Uncertainty analysis	10 resample cycles, 10000 MC simulations

Results

Exposure distribution (model based) percentiles.

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	0.026535	0.026589	1.00
90	0.46408	0.46809	0.99
95	0.94324	0.94487	1.00
99	3.4229	3.4642	0.99
99.9	12.747	14.231	0.90
99.99	43.777	56.994	0.77

Differences in percentiles in 'model based' percentiles are the result of code changes which have altered the propagation of random seeding. Running the project with different seeds gives the same variance in resulting percentiles with the same version of MCRA.

A.3.29 Validation test 29: Chronic exposure assessment, model LNN

Chronic, long term exposure assessment, LNN.

Settings

See A.3.28, but with model LNN (no correlation).

Results

Results for dietary exposures distribution, model based

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	0.031835	0.031817	1.00
90	0.48255	0.47866	1.01
95	0.97351	0.96308	1.01
99	3.3306	3.2902	1.01
99.9	12.19	12.18	1.00
99.99	27.751	31.851	0.87

Differences in percentiles in 'model based' percentiles are the result of code changes which have altered the propagation of random seeding. Running the project with different seeds gives the same variance in resulting percentiles with the same version of MCRA.

Results for dietary exposures distribution, model assisted

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	0.040194	0.040194	1.00
90	0.50378	0.50378	1.00
95	0.97079	0.97079	1.00
99	4.018	4.018	1.00
99.9	10.457	10.457	1.00
99.99	15.754	15.754	1.00

A.3.30 Validation test 30: Chronic exposure assessment, model OIM

Chronic, long term exposure assessment, Observed Individual Means model.

Settings

Data	
Single data-source	ValidationMCRA7.mdb
Select	
Food consumption survey	DNFCS-3
Substance	CAPTAN
Model	
Exposure calculation tier	Custom
Dietary exposures method	Distribution estimates
Exposure model-type	Observed Individual Means
Concentration model	Empirical, nondetects set to zero. fixed processing factors
Uncertainty analysis	10 resample cycles

Results

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	0.00082803	0.00082803	1.00
90	0.38834	0.38834	1.00
95	0.93228	0.93228	1.00
99	3.3666	3.3666	1.00
99.9	9.9668	9.9668	1.00
99.99	15.747	15.747	1.00

A.3.31 Validation test 31: Chronic exposure assessment, model-then-add

Chronic, long term exposure assessment, model-then-add.

Settings

Data	
Single data-source	2012 - Rookaroma.mdb
Select	
Food consumption survey	VCP-basis
Model	
Exposure calculation tier	Custom
Dietary exposures method	Distribution estimates
Exposure model-type	Model-then-add
Concentration model	Empirical, nondetects set to zero. fixed processing factors.
Uncertainty analysis	10 resample cycles

Results

Results for dietary exposures distribution, model based

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	184.76	170.35	1.08
90	472.98	555.38	0.85
95	638.58	891.26	0.72
99	1225.9	1169.4	1.05
99.9	2255.5	2271.3	0.99
99.99	3553.2	3521.1	1.01

Differences in percentiles in 'model based' percentiles are the result of code changes which have altered the propagation of random seeding. Running the project with different seeds gives the same variance in resulting percentiles with the same version of MCRA.

Results for dietary exposures distribution, model assisted

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	202.77	202.77	1.00
90	411.2	411.2	1.00
95	516.44	516.44	1.00
99	1057.9	1057.9	1.00
99.9	2074	2074	1.00

99.99	3176.9	3176.9	1.00
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A.3.32 Validation test 32: TDS Chronic, long term exposure assessment

TDS Chronic, long term exposure assessment. Food subset active, no selected foods.

Settings

Data	
Single data-source	TDS data 2.mdb
Select	
Food consumption survey	NVS2
Substance	Total manganese
Model	
Exposure calculation tier	Custom
Dietary exposures method	Distribution estimates
Exposure model-type	Observed Individual Means
Concentration model	Summary statistics, nondetects set to 0 * LOR. fixed processing factors.
Uncertainty analysis	10 resample cycles

Results

Observed Individual Means model, dietary, percentiles

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	38.124	38.124	1.00
90	66.67	66.67	1.00
95	78.548	78.548	1.00
97.5	90.928	90.928	1.00
99	107.14	107.14	1.00
99.9	157.72	157.72	1.00
99.99	185.94	185.94	1.00

A.3.33 Validation test 33: TDS Chronic, long term exposure assessment, Multigrain B+R

TDS Chronic, long term exposure assessment. Food subset active on 'Multigrain bread and rolls'.

Settings

Same as in A.3.32, with food as measured subset on 'Multigrain bread and rolls'.

Results

Observed Individual Means model, dietary, percentiles

Percentile	MCRA 8	MCRA 9	Ratio MCRA 8 / MCRA 9
50	39.892	39.892	1.00
90	67.732	67.732	1.00
95	79.22	79.22	1.00
97.5	91.985	91.985	1.00

99	107.78	107.78	1.00
99.9	159.22	159.22	1.00
99.99	182.82	182.82	1.00